

**Asymptotic and numerical analysis of
resonances in circular and elliptic quantum
potentials**

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Declaration

No part of the work referred to in this thesis has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other university or institute of learning.

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Abstract

The complex wavenumber plane endows us with a natural setting in which to appreciate and trace the behaviour of the various types of solutions of the time-independent Schrödinger equation in response to changes in the parameters of the potential. When this is done for simple potential systems in one and two dimensions, surprisingly rich dynamics emerge, such as the presence of attracting points, and interesting inter-conversions between the various kinds of solutions. Simple one dimensional square potentials, both attractive and repulsive were treated first. The calculations were then performed for a 2D cylindrical barrier, a cylindrical well, and the case of a slightly elliptic barrier potential. This work is a systematic study of resonance trajectories in the complex wavenumber plane, and an additional complex potentiodynamic plane, which is more suited to studying the asymptotic behaviour of the states as the potential becomes infinitely high, or infinitely deep. We investigate the behaviour of bound states, external and internal resonances and antiresonances, and antibound states.

Modern computational approaches to complex transcendental root finding were implemented and combined to provide us with robust and tunable tools for conducting the numerical work. A library of Mathieu functions of complex parameters was created (as no such library exists in commercially available software at present), which gave us the freedom to study an elliptic potential in the complex k plane.

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Chapter 1

Introduction and Theory

1.1 Resonances

Resonances arise in quantum mechanics in the context of the scattering of particles from a potential system. In 1921, the physicists Ramsauer and Townsend fired electrons at a noble gas target. They were surprised to observe that for certain values of electron momentum, transmission through the target was essentially 100%. It was not until several years later that the pioneers of quantum mechanics made the ideas of potential wells, bound states, and resonances precise enough to explain the Ramsauer-Townsend effect - a phenomenon completely beyond the reach of classical physics (Robinett, 2006).

The essential facets of resonance theory can be clearly elucidated in one dimension (Griffiths, 2004; Shankar, 1994). Consider a potential of finite range, R as shown in Fig. (1.1). We place a hard wall (infinite barrier) for all $x \leq 0$, because this scenario closely models the situation of higher dimensional scattering, where the distance, r , from the scattering centre is always non-negative. If we ignore the influence of the potential for $x \leq R$, and consider simply a free particle with an infinite wall at the origin, particles incident on the infinite wall from the right with definite momentum $\hbar k$

Figure 1.1: An arbitrary one-dimensional potential $V(x)$ of finite range, R , with hard wall (infinite barrier) for all $x \leq 0$ shown in grey. Particles are incident on the potential from the right, and are reflected back along that direction after interacting with the system. This is a typical example of a potential that can support permanent bound states, shown as thin black lines for negatives energies, as well as metastable resonances, shown as thick lines for positive energies.

would be represented by e^{-ikx} , and the reflected particles would travel to the right with no loss of energy, with representation e^{ikx} . To account for the effect of the infinite wall, we require that the energy eigenstate built out of these plane waves vanishes at the origin. This suggests the combination $\psi_0(x) \propto e^{ikx} - e^{-ikx}$, as this vanishes for $x = 0$. A convenient normalisation would then be

$$\psi_0(x) = \frac{e^{ikx}}{2i} - \frac{e^{-ikx}}{2i} = \sin(kx). \quad (1.1)$$

This homogeneous solution $\psi_0(x)$ can be separated into component parts as

$$\begin{cases} \text{incoming} & : -\frac{e^{-ikx}}{2i}, \\ \text{outgoing} & : \frac{e^{ikx}}{2i}. \end{cases}$$

If we now restore the potential $V(x)$, which differs from the free particle case only for $x \leq R$, it follows that the incoming component must be the same as before, but that the outgoing piece must be affected by the interaction with $V(x)$. To ensure that the outgoing wave has the same energy as the incoming wave and remains a valid solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation, the only thing that can change is modulation by a phase factor. The canonical way to write this outgoing wave is as

$$e^{2i\delta} \frac{e^{ikx}}{2i}, \quad (x > R).$$

Then the full solution $\psi(x)$, valid only for $x > R$, will be given by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x) &= \frac{e^{ikx+2i\delta}}{2i} - \frac{e^{-ikx}}{2i} \\ &= \frac{e^{i\delta}}{2i} (e^{i(kx+\delta)} - e^{-i(kx+\delta)}) \\ &= e^{i\delta} \sin(kx + \delta), \quad (x > R). \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

The total solution can then be thought of as the homogeneous solution $\psi_0(x)$ (with no potential) plus a *scattered* solution $\psi_s(x)$ that arises from interaction with the potential,

and that vanishes if the potential is switched off, reducing to the homogeneous case. That is

$$\psi(x) = \psi_0(x) + \psi_s(x).$$

Accordingly, we can solve for the scattered solution ψ_s using Eqs. (1.1) and (1.2). This gives, for $x > R$,

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_s(x) &= \psi(x) - \psi_0(x) \\ &= \frac{e^{ikx+2i\delta}}{2i} - \frac{e^{-ikx}}{2i} - \frac{e^{ikx}}{2i} + \frac{e^{-ikx}}{2i} \\ &= \frac{1}{2i} (e^{ikx+2i\delta} - e^{ikx}) \\ &= \frac{e^{i\delta}}{2i} (e^{i\delta} - e^{-i\delta}) e^{ikx} \\ &= e^{i\delta} \sin(\delta) e^{ikx} \\ &= A_s e^{ikx}. \end{aligned} \tag{1.3}$$

In Eq. (1.3), we identify $A_s = e^{i\delta} \sin(\delta)$ as the scattering amplitude, and note that the scattered wave is, as expected, an outgoing wave. This is the piece of the full solution that arises due to the presence of a non-zero potential, and contains the useful information about that potential.

For the purposes of this work, we are interested in the bound states and resonances of such potentials. Fig. (1.1) shows a typical example of a finite range potential that can support both resonances and bound states. Bound states are stable, negative-energy eigensolutions of the time-independent Schrödinger equation. Resonances can be conceptualised as *metastable* states, or temporary trapped states. One can think of particles as becoming temporarily captured by the potential, but eventually escaping *via* quantum tunnelling. To see why this is true, we compare the absolute squares of

the amplitudes of the wavefunctions $\psi(x)$, and $\psi_0(x)$, that is

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_0(x)|^2 &= \sin^2(kx), \\ |\psi(x)|^2 &= \sin^2(kx + \delta). \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

A feature present at argument α for the homogeneous wavefunction $|\psi_0(x)|^2$ is found at $x = \alpha/k$. The same feature is found at $x = \alpha/k - \delta/k$ in the wavefunction $|\psi(x)|^2$ when there is a non-zero potential. Then for a positive phase shift, δ , one can see that the potential has the effect of shifting the probability density towards the potential, *i.e.* the potential is *attractive*. The notion of being trapped by the potential can be made more precise by constructing wave-packets for the incident and reflected components of the total wavefunction $\Psi(x, t)$. Since we are working with stationary states, these wave-packets can be built using Fourier representations, as

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_i(x, t) &= \int_0^\infty dk \tilde{f}(k) e^{-ikx} e^{-iE(k)t/\hbar}, & x > R, \\ \Psi_r(x, t) &= - \int_0^\infty dk \tilde{f}(k) e^{ikx} e^{2i\delta(k)} e^{-iE(k)t/\hbar}, & x > R. \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

These representations of localised wave-packets require that the function $\tilde{f}(k)$ has compact support about a value $k = k_0$. This means the majority contribution to the integral must happen around k_0 , so the overall phase must be slowly varying in this region to produce a significant amplitude. Hence, applying the method of stationary phase to the reflected wave-packet gives

$$\left. \frac{d}{dk} \left(kx + 2\delta(k) - \frac{\hbar k^2}{2m} t \right) \right|_{k=k_0} = 0. \tag{1.6}$$

After some simple manipulation, using the fact that the group velocity of a wave-packet is $v_g = \hbar k/m$, we are led to the fact that

$$x = v_g \left(t - 2\hbar \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right). \tag{1.7}$$

The reflected packet will not emerge from the potential until $t > 2\hbar\delta'(E)$. This is the *time delay*. After some more trivial algebra with the time delay, Δt , the condition

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{d\delta}{dk} = \frac{\Delta t}{\left(\frac{2R}{v_g}\right)} \quad (1.8)$$

emerges. The expression $2R/v_g$ is simply the *free transit time* of a particle back and forth over the range of a potential if the particle experienced no effects of the potential. Then this is a convenient, unit free expression of the time delay experienced by a particle over a potential of range R .

The idea of a resonance is now coming more clearly into focus. Resonances are associated with trapped particles that form meta-stable states, and take some time to emerge from the potential (Gamow, 1928; Siegert, 1939). The phase shift $\delta(k)$ then contains the information we need to find resonances. If one takes a typical potential like that shown in Fig. (1.1) and examines the phase shift, $\delta(k)$, the square of the scattering amplitude $|A_s|^2$ and the time-delay $\delta'(k)/R$ as functions of k , certain identifying features appear at resonance. The plot of the phase shift has a characteristic sharp jump of approximately π near resonance. The squared scattering amplitude has a sharp peak at resonance which reaches close to $|A_s|^2 = 1$. The time delay will also have a peak at resonant wavenumbers which illustrates the fact we argued before - that particles with resonant wavenumbers become temporarily trapped by the potential.

To find resonances, we capture the aforementioned features by modelling the phase shift using the function

$$\delta(k) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha - k} \right). \quad (1.9)$$

where $\alpha, \beta > 0$. This function possesses the typical features in the various quantities involving the phase shift near resonance. The time delay is given by this model as

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{d\delta}{dk} = \frac{\beta^2}{R(\alpha - k)^2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta^2}{(\alpha - k)^2} \right)}. \quad (1.10)$$

The square of the scattering amplitude is then modelled as

$$|A_s|^2 = \sin^2 \delta = \frac{\beta^2}{\beta^2 + (\alpha - k)^2}, \quad (1.11)$$

using the identity $\sin(\arctan x) = x/\sqrt{x^2 + 1}$. This is the so-called Breit-Wigner Distribution in terms of the wavenumber, k . More canonically, this is expressed in terms of energy. To do this, we note that $E = \hbar^2 k^2/2m$, and the energy at resonance $k = \alpha$ is $E = \hbar^2 \alpha^2/2m$. Then

$$\Delta E = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}(k^2 - \alpha^2). \quad (1.12)$$

Noting the difference of squares $k^2 - \alpha^2 = (k + \alpha)(k - \alpha)$, we also make the reasonable approximation that near resonance, when $k \approx \alpha$, we can write $k + \alpha \approx 2\alpha$. Then

$$\Delta E = \frac{\hbar^2}{m}\alpha(k - \alpha). \quad (1.13)$$

Hence, substitution of $(\alpha - k)^2$ into Eq. (1.11) yields, at resonance

$$|A_s|^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\hbar^2 \alpha \beta}{m}\right)^2}{\Delta E^2 + \left(\frac{\hbar^2 \alpha \beta}{m}\right)^2}. \quad (1.14)$$

It is conventional to define the full width at half maximum for the distribution as

$$\Gamma = \frac{2\hbar^2 \alpha \beta}{m}, \quad (1.15)$$

with which we can display the Breit-Wigner Distribution in terms of energy as

$$|A_s|^2 = \frac{\frac{1}{4}\Gamma^2}{\Delta E^2 + \frac{1}{4}\Gamma^2}. \quad (1.16)$$

The essential features of the phase shift related quantities near a resonance $k = \alpha$

Figure 1.2: Plots of various quantities related to the phase shift $\delta(k)$ near resonance $k = \alpha$. Subfig (a) shows $\tan \delta$, subfig (b) shows δ itself, subfig (c) shows the time delay $\delta'(k)$, and subfig (d) shows the absolute square of the scattering amplitude $|A_s|^2$. These capture the essential behaviour of the phase shift near a resonance. Here, example values of $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 0.1$ were used to produce the figures.

are shown in Fig. (1.2).

With this model in mind we consider again the scattering amplitude

$$A_s = e^{i\delta} \sin \delta = \frac{\sin \delta}{e^{-i\delta}} = \frac{\sin \delta}{\cos \delta - i \sin \delta}. \quad (1.17)$$

Dividing through by $\cos \delta$, one finds that

$$A_s = \frac{\tan \delta}{1 - i \tan \delta}. \quad (1.18)$$

Using the model for the phase shift in Eq. (1.9), we have

$$A_s = \frac{\frac{\beta}{\alpha - k}}{1 - i \frac{\beta}{\alpha - k}} = \frac{\beta}{(\alpha - i\beta) - k}. \quad (1.19)$$

Then one notes that the scattering amplitude has a pole in the *complex* wavenumber plane at $k = \alpha - i\beta$. Hence we are led inexorably to the idea of complex wavenumbers in our analysis. Since $\alpha, \beta > 0$, this means that the scattering amplitude blows up at points in the 4th quadrant of the $k \in \mathbb{C}$ plane. These are the points we identify as *resonances* (Dyatlov and Zworski, 2019; Johnson, 2017).

The complex plane is more useful than even this, for if we have $k = i\kappa$, where $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}$, the energy is

$$E = \frac{\hbar^2 (i\kappa)^2}{2m} = -\frac{\hbar^2 \kappa^2}{2m} < 0, \quad (1.20)$$

so we see that even *bound* states are found in the complex k plane, on the upper half imaginary axis. Indeed, the complex k plane contains the bound states, resonances, *antiresonances* and *antibound* states of potentials. Antibound states are like bound states that match onto growing exponentials in the classically forbidden region, and are associated with certain nuclear states, see (Michel et al., 2006; Ohanian and Ginsburg, 1974). Antiresonances are time-reversal symmetry partners of the resonances, and satisfy the condition $k_{\text{antires}} = (-k_{\text{res}})^*$ for resonant wavenumbers. A schematic of the k

plane is shown in Fig. (1.3) showing the typical positions of each type of state (Sprung et al., 1996).

Figure 1.3: The complex k plane showing the typical positions of each type of state. The red {green} dots on the positive {negative} imaginary axis are {anti} bound states. The blue {purple} dots in quadrant four {three} are {anti}resonances.

The resonance $k = \alpha - i\beta$ can be viewed in terms of complex energy as follows:

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}(\alpha^2 - \beta^2) - i\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\hbar^2 \alpha \beta}{m} \right), \quad (1.21)$$

or, using the resonance width Γ , we can write

$$\mathcal{E} = E - \frac{1}{2}i\Gamma, \quad \Gamma > 0. \quad (1.22)$$

Our central objective will be to locate the resonances for potentials of various geometries by locating poles of the scattering amplitude. Knowledge of the locations of the complete set of all resonances for all combinations of potential parameters is highly useful for techniques such as Resonant State Expansion (RSE) (Muljarov et al., 2010;

Doost et al., 2013, 2014; Tanimu and Muljarov, 2018). We will then investigate the dependence of the positions of the states in response to varying parameters of the potential. The trajectories traced out as parameters are varied to produce subtle and rich structure, and the interplay between the types of states is incredibly interesting. Understanding resonances in nature is of paramount importance given the privileged position they occupy in mathematics, physics and engineering. For instance, it is well known that resonances are particularly important in relation to microcavity lasers, biosensing, semiconductor nanostructures and photonics to name but a few (Matsko, 2009; Jokerst et al., 2009; Zhu et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2017; Ward and Benson, 2011; Limonov et al., 2017; Heebner et al., 2008).

1.2 Complex root finding

1.2.1 Wagon’s method

The need to find complex roots of transcendental resonance conditions necessitates the use of a procedure for locating zeros that can be fully controlled by the user. A powerful grid-search based method for two-dimensional root finding was designed by Wagon (Wagon, 2010), and can be adapted to deal with complex functions.

The idea behind the procedure is to find simultaneous roots of two functions $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$. We evaluate both functions over a mesh and construct contour plots for both showing only the zero levels. One then extracts the points along the zero levels of one of the functions, and steps along these level curves, checking the *sign* of the other function at each point along the zero levels of the first. Where the second function changes sign, we must be close to a root of both functions. We refer to these points as *seeds*, and these seeds are then fed to some root-finding method, such as the Newton-Raphson procedure, Muller’s method, or the robust Davidenko’s method, which are

outlined later. All of these methods are rapidly convergent when fed a good initial candidate point.

Wagon's method provides both an efficient way to generate seeds for the root finding procedures, and serves as a visual check that all suspected points found are indeed true roots - and that none are missing, by appearing as clear crossing points of zero level contours of both functions.

As a demonstration, let us consider the example real system

$$\begin{cases} u(x, y) = -x \cos(y) + 2y \cos(y^2) \cos(2x), \\ v(x, y) = -\sin(x) + 2 \sin(y^2) \sin(2x). \end{cases} \quad (1.23)$$

To apply Wagon's algorithm, the steps are:

1. Evaluate both u and v over a rectangular mesh of points defined by the inequalities $x_{\min} \leq x \leq x_{\max}$ and $y_{\min} \leq y \leq y_{\max}$.
2. Plot the zero levels of both curves, and save the points of one set of zero levels, say those for u .
3. For every point (x_j^*, y_j^*) along the saved zero levels, evaluate and store $\text{sgn}[v(x_j^*, y_j^*)]$.
4. To check for a sign change, take sequential differences over the array of stored signs. Sign changes happen when this difference is non-zero, since

$$\text{sgn}(x) := \begin{cases} -1, & x < 0, \\ 0, & x = 0, \\ 1, & x > 0. \end{cases}$$

5. The (x_j^*, y_j^*) where sign changes occur are root candidates (*seeds*) for the system.

Feed these into a root finding method as initial guesses, and rapid convergence should occur.

6. Visually inspect the graphical output to check that the roots are all associated with crossings of zero levels and that none are missing.

An example graphical output of the procedure applied to Eqs. (1.23) is shown in Fig. (1.4), which clearly shows that all crossings have been accounted for, and that no roots are missing, so we have located all roots within the specified domain. Usually we will not display the seeds when this procedure is used, but they are shown in Fig. (1.4) as a demonstration that we already found the approximate locations of zeros before applying any iterative methods.

Figure 1.4: Illustration of Wagon’s method in the (x, y) plane. The blue {orange} curves are the zero levels for $u(x, y) = -x \cos(y) + 2y \cos(y^2) \cos(2x)$ $\{v(x, y) = -\sin(x) + 2 \sin(y^2) \sin(2x)\}$. The seeds are shown as green dots, and the true roots are shown as red dots.

This procedure can be easily adapted to deal with complex functions by simply viewing the complex function $f(z) = u(x, y) + iv(x, y)$ as a two-dimensional real system. This works because zeros of f necessitate the vanishing of both real and imaginary parts. Hence, we apply Wagon’s method to the equivalent real system

$$\begin{cases} u(x, y) = 0, \\ v(x, y) = 0. \end{cases}$$

This algorithm can be made very efficient if one parallelises the bottle-necked step, which is the evaluation of the pair of functions over the mesh. This can be done simply by partitioning the grid into sub-grids determined by the available number of threads on a machine. There are, however, much more efficient ways to mesh the region than naive rectangulation (see Chapter 6 for a discussion about ongoing efforts).

1.2.2 Domain colouring

Wagon’s method can be extended further by adding *domain colouring*. This is a technique useful for visualising the 4 dimensional space needed to properly understand complex functions (Wegert, 2012). One considers an input plane, z , and an output plane $w = f(z)$. The output plane can be colour mapped such that the colours cycle precisely once about the origin $w = 0$, as shown in Fig. (1.6)(a). One can think of taking all the points from the z plane, and mapping them into the w plane under f . Where they land in the w plane selects the colour they inherit, and one can imagine the points being ‘painted’ by the w plane, under the map $\mathcal{C}(w)$, before returning to their original positions in the z plane with their colour designations. Fig. (1.5) shows how this works for a simple mapping $z \mapsto z^2$. These maps give useful insight into the function f , as coordinate axes in the w plane are mapped to from the zero levels of f in the z plane, *i.e.* the zero contours of f are the preimage of the coordinate axes of the w plane. Moreover, the cycling of colours about the origin of the w plane carries over

Figure 1.5: Domain colour map for example function $z \mapsto z^2$, showing a point in the z plane mapping to the w plane under f , where it acquires the colour green in the z plane under the colour map $\mathcal{C}(w)$. The complex square function causes the phase to cycle twice about the origin, as can be seen in the left-hand image. The colour map in the w plane was set manually to assign RGB values to each quadrant in the output w plane.

into at least one full colour cycle about the positions of the zeros of f in the z plane, with the total number of colour cycles corresponding to the multiplicity of that zero. This domain colouring can be added to Wagon’s method as a further check that no roots have been missed (Kowalczyk, 2018), see Fig.(1.6)(b), and compare the positions of the zeros with those in Fig.(1.4).

1.2.3 Davidenko’s method

A second highly useful root finding method for complex functions is the method of Davidenko. This method has been successfully applied in physics, see for example (Hejase, 1993). Loosely speaking, this method transforms the problem of finding roots to the numerical integration of a system of two coupled non-linear ordinary differential equations (ODEs) in a parameter t . To see how this works, one begins with the Newton-Raphson procedure, wherein one takes the equation of a straight line through an initial

(a)

(b)

Figure 1.6: Domain colouring maps of (a) the w plane, with colours cycling once about the origin, showing $\text{Re } w$ and $\text{Im } w = 0$ and (b) the input z plane, showing the zero levels and positions of the roots of $w = f(z)$. The zero levels in the z plane map to the real and imaginary axes in the w plane under f .

candidate point $(x_0, f(x_0))$,

$$f(x) - f(x_0) = f'(x_0)(x - x_0). \quad (1.24)$$

Seeking solutions to $f(x) = 0$, we obtain the iteration formula

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{f(x_n)}{f'(x_n)}. \quad (1.25)$$

This can be generalized to a system $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}$ by expanding to first order and using the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x})$ as

$$\mathbf{x}_{n+1} = \mathbf{x}_n - \mathbf{J}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_n)\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_n). \quad (1.26)$$

Equivalently, one can write $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}_n)\Delta\mathbf{x}_n = -\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_n)$. Then it is clear that Newton's method proceeds *via* finite steps $|\Delta\mathbf{x}_n|$. The power of Davidenko's method, is that it is a *differential* form of Newton's method that can be written as

$$\mathbf{J} \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = -\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.27)$$

in which t is a real parameter introduced to produce a continuous analogue of the finite steps in Newton's method. The conventional way to apply this method is to cast the system as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.28)$$

subject to an initial condition $\mathbf{x}(0) = (x_0 \ y_0)^T$. One can now use any of the readily available efficient numerical integrators in scientific computing packages. Because this method proceeds *via* differential steps, it may converge where the finite stepping Newton method fails to. Moreover, the algorithm is inherently stable, because numerical integration of ODEs is a robust and well established practice.

Formulating this procedure explicitly for the relevant case of a complex holomorphic

function $f(z) = u(x, y) + iv(x, y)$, we have from Eq. (1.27)

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{dx}{dt} \\ \frac{dy}{dt} \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} u(x, y) \\ v(x, y) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.29)$$

By applying the Cauchy-Riemann conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} &= -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.30)$$

since we expect that relevant f will have regions of analyticity, this system can be inverted to yield a coupled ODE for the derivatives of the real and imaginary arguments x and y with respect to the dummy parameter, t . That is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{dx}{dt} \\ \frac{dy}{dt} \end{pmatrix} = -\frac{1}{u_x^2 + v_x^2} \begin{pmatrix} u_x & v_x \\ -v_x & u_x \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.31)$$

But $u_x^2 + v_x^2 = |f'(z)|^2$, $u_x = \operatorname{Re}f'(z)$, and $v_x = \operatorname{Im}f'(z)$. Hence, writing everything concretely, Davidenko's method involves numerical integration of the ODE system

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= -\frac{\operatorname{Re}f'(z)\operatorname{Re}f(z) + \operatorname{Im}f'(z)\operatorname{Im}f(z)}{|f'(z)|^2}, \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= \frac{\operatorname{Im}f'(z)\operatorname{Re}f(z) - \operatorname{Re}f'(z)\operatorname{Im}f(z)}{|f'(z)|^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (1.32)$$

subject to $x(0) = x_0, y(0) = y_0$, the initial seed.

Wagon's method can be used to locate reasonable seeds for Davidenko's method, providing a highly reliable root finding procedure. The only drawback to this method is that, like Newton's method, one must have a closed form expression for the derivative of $f(z)$.

1.2.4 Müller's method

For cases where the function $f(z)$ is so complicated that it is either prohibitively difficult to take a derivative, or computationally expensive to evaluate the derivative, a convenient option is Müller's method (Chapra and Canale, 2006). Müller's method is also particularly well suited to complex root finding, because unlike Newton's method, which requires a complex seed to converge to a complex root, Müller's method has no such restriction. The method is essentially a higher order version of the Secant method, in that it uses a 3 point quadratic interpolation to iteratively find roots of f , instead of the linear interpolation used by the Secant method, which itself is an analogue of Newton's method that uses finite differences instead of the derivative. Instead of requiring one function call, and one derivative call for each iterate, Müller's method requires 3 initial candidate points $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$, which can then be iterated in a rolling manner, such that the next step uses $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$, and so on. This method has the slower convergence rate of 1.84 compared to 2 for Newton's method, but avoids the complication of requiring the derivative completely. This convergence rate refers to the power of the error term in the approximation, so the error goes to zero faster in Newton's method than Müller's method. The main idea behind the procedure is shown for an example real function in Fig. (1.7). To see where this method comes from, we can write the interpolating parabola as

$$\tilde{f}(x) = A(x - x_2)^2 + B(x - x_2) + C. \quad (1.33)$$

We note that we require a parabola intersecting x_0, x_1 and x_2 , which leads to the system

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{f}(x_0) &= A(x_0 - x_2)^2 + B(x_0 - x_2) + C \\ \tilde{f}(x_1) &= A(x_1 - x_2)^2 + B(x_1 - x_2) + C \\ \tilde{f}(x_2) &= C. \end{aligned} \quad (1.34)$$

Figure 1.7: Müller's method for an example real function, f , shown in blue, with three initial points $\{x_0, x_1, x_2\}$ fit by a parabola, \tilde{f} , shown in red. The intersection of the parabola with the x axis is taken as x_3 , an approximation of the root, and the process is iterated using $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$. The process is repeated with the goal of finding a suitable numerical approximation of the true root x_* .

This is a system of 2 equations in 2 unknowns A and B , since C is determined by simple substitution. Solving for these coefficients algebraically, one can then apply the quadratic formula to Eq. (1.33) to calculate the roots of the interpolating parabola, keeping only the one which produces the smaller value of $f(x)$. This procedure is then continued with the next set of points $\{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$, where x_3 is the aforementioned retained root. The procedure is repeated until satisfactory convergence is attained, or until some cut-off point, beyond which we say the procedure failed to converge. In this work, all of the root finding procedures mentioned were used in various combinations as appropriate, to confirm the veracity of solutions.

Figure 1.8: The Levinson contour with outer radius R , and inner radius ε in the $k \in \mathbb{C}$ plane, for applying the Argument Principle to count bound states.

1.3 Exploiting the complex plane

That the complex k plane has naturally appeared as the appropriate arena for analysing resonances and bound states is fortuitous, as now we can bring to bear the full arsenal of techniques from complex analysis. We previously reasoned that poles of the scattering amplitude, or equivalently zeros of the resonance condition, that correspond to bound states appear as purely imaginary points in the upper half k plane. We can use the Argument Principle (Ahlfors, 1979) to count the number of solutions within a region before any root finding is used. One convenient idea is to use a contour in $k \in \mathbb{C}$, that we refer to as the Levinson contour, shown in Fig. (1.8) (Ma, 2006; Burke and Joachain, 1995). The Argument Principle tells us that the number of zeros, \mathcal{N} , of a holomorphic function $f(z)$, counted according to their orders in a domain \mathcal{D} enclosed by a contour Γ is given by a contour integral of the logarithmic derivative of f around Γ , *i.e.*

$$\mathcal{N} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{\Gamma} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} dz, \quad (1.35)$$

where Γ is a closed contour in $\mathbb{C} - \{\alpha_j\}$, where $\{\alpha_j\}$ are the zeros of f . In other words, the contour itself must not pass through any zeros. The proof of this statement follows from recognising that if $f(z)$ is holomorphic and has a zero of order n at the point α , we can write

$$f(z) = (z - \alpha)^n g(z), \quad (1.36)$$

where $g(\alpha) \neq 0$, and g is holomorphic at α . Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} &= \frac{n(z - \alpha)^{n-1}g(z) + g'(z)(z - \alpha)^n}{(z - \alpha)^n g(z)} \\ &= \frac{n}{z - \alpha} + \frac{g'(z)}{g(z)}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.37)$$

Therefore, $\text{Res}(f'/f, \alpha) = n$. Using the fact highlighted in Eq. (1.37), the Argument Principle can be proved by invoking the Residue Theorem applied to a contour Γ surrounding $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_N\}$, which are zeros of f . Then

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{\Gamma} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} dz = \sum_{j=1}^N \text{Res} \left(\frac{f'(z)}{f(z)}, z = \alpha_j \right) = n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_N, \quad (1.38)$$

where n_j is the order of the zero α_j .

The Argument Principle applied to the resonance condition in the k plane, using the Levinson contour as shown in Fig. (1.8) is a statement of Levinson's Theorem, which gives us an elegant method for counting the bound states of a potential.

The resonance conditions for the various potentials in this work will be solved numerically using the root finding methods discussed previously. Therefore, a useful extension of Wagon's Procedure will be to build a numerical recipe for Levinson's Theorem directly into the procedure to count the number of solutions within some domain, which is a useful way to show that no solutions are missing. This also acts as a mitigation against false zeros that result in the vicinity of branch cuts, since non-integer values of Eq. (1.35) imply that the contour chosen was not closed, *i.e.* suggesting that multiple

Figure 1.9: Small loop contour, \mathcal{C} , of radius ε about centre α with contour partitioned into sub-paths $\{\gamma_p\}$.

Riemann sheets must be present.

To apply the Argument Principle numerically, let us consider a circular contour \mathcal{C} with centre α for simplicity. We break the path \mathcal{C} into a union of sub-paths, *i.e.*

$$\mathcal{C} = \bigcup_{p=1}^P \gamma_p. \quad (1.39)$$

By writing $f(z) = R(z) \exp(i\varphi(z))$, the integrand of Eq. (1.35) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} &= \frac{[R'(z) + i\varphi'(z)R(z)] \exp(i\varphi(z))}{R(z) \exp(i\varphi(z))} \\ &= \frac{R'(z)}{R(z)} + i\varphi'(z). \end{aligned} \quad (1.40)$$

It is then easy to see by referring to Fig.(1.9) that the contour integral around the

circle \mathcal{C} of the logarithmic derivative of f is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{C}} &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \oint_{\Gamma} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} dz \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{p=1}^P \int_{\gamma_p} \frac{f'(z)}{f(z)} dz \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \sum_{p=1}^P \int_{\gamma_p} \left(\frac{R'(z)}{R(z)} + \varphi'(z) \right) dz \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left\{ \sum_{p=1}^{P-1} \left[\ln \left(\frac{R(z_{p+1})}{R(z_p)} \right) + i(\varphi(z_{p+1}) - \varphi(z_p)) \right] + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \ln \left(\frac{R(z_1)}{R(z_P)} \right) + i(\varphi(z_1) - \varphi(z_P)) \right\}. \tag{1.41}
\end{aligned}$$

But the series in Eq. (1.41) is a telescoping series. For numerical purposes we will opt to retain the argument terms φ and perform the actual summation of the imaginary part, even though this too is telescoping, because we must allow the argument to accumulate. The numerical procedure is then

$$\mathcal{N}_{\mathcal{C}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{p=1}^P \Delta\varphi(z_p). \tag{1.42}$$

This form of the Argument Principle can be readily implemented as a computational routine (Kowalczyk, 2015), and we can use it to numerically implement Levinson's Theorem, using contour Γ and Eq. (1.42).

An additional benefit to this numerical routine is that it can be used to augment the Wagon's method. The veracity of a root proposed by Wagon's method can be established by checking that this winding number contour integral returns positive integer values. Root finding procedures can sometimes have trouble distinguishing between zeros and various types of singular points, such as poles and branch points, and this extra check gives us the means to do this in an automated and reliable way.

Chapter 2

One Dimensional Square Systems

A reasonable first step towards studying the elliptic two-dimensional potentials that are the apex of this work is to first treat well known one-dimensional systems and recapitulate known results (Belchev et al., 2011; Nussenzveig, 1959). This will serve to demonstrate the use of the numerical procedures, and to introduce the terminology used in the later analyses. We also present some new ways of visualising the data that will be important for the subsequent chapters. The results of this chapter were published in *Physics Letters A* (Meeten and Morozov, 2020a).

2.1 Square well

We begin the analysis by setting up the square well potential, centred at the origin, of width $2a$ and depth V_0 . That is

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} -V_0, & |x| < a, \\ 0, & |x| > a. \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.1: Schematic of the square well potential, with width $2a$ and depth $-V_0$.

A schematic of the well is shown in Figure 2.1. We are interested primarily in the resonances of such a potential, and in particular how they vary in the complex plane as the well depth is changed. We seek eigensolutions of the time-independent Schrödinger equation

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2M} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + V(x) \right] \psi_n(x) = \mathcal{E}_n \psi_n(x), \quad (2.2)$$

where \mathcal{E}_n is the complex energy eigenvalue, which we defined in Eq. (1.22) as

$$\mathcal{E}_n = E_n - \frac{1}{2}i\Gamma_n, \quad \Gamma_n \geq 0, \quad (2.3)$$

subject to continuity of the logarithmic derivative at the boundaries, $x = \pm a$, and the outgoing wave condition which gives the asymptotic behaviour of the coordinate wavefunctions as

$$\psi_n(x) \sim e^{ik_n x}, \quad x \rightarrow \infty, \quad (2.4)$$

where $k_n = \alpha_n + i\beta_n$. The signs of α_n, β_n determine whether we have bound/antibound states or resonances/antiresonances.

For convenience, we work throughout in Rydberg units, where the mass of the particle $M = 1/2$ and the reduced Planck constant, \hbar is set to 1. We also set a to 1. The eigenproblem can then be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + k^2 \right] \psi(x) &= 0, & k &= \sqrt{\mathcal{E}}, & |x| &> a, \\ \left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \kappa^2 \right] \psi(x) &= 0, & \kappa &= \sqrt{k^2 + V_0}, & |x| &< a. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Since energy eigenstates are *stationary* states, *i.e.* states whose time dependence factors as $\Psi(x, t) = \psi(x) \exp(-i\mathcal{E}t)$, one can write the total wavefunctions $\Psi_n(x, t)$ of resonances as

$$\Psi_n(x, t) = \psi_n(x) \exp(-iE_n t) \exp\left(-\frac{\Gamma_n}{2} t\right), \quad (2.6)$$

which clearly shows that resonances are states that decay in time. We require physically reasonable solutions to obey time-reversal symmetry, *i.e.* such states should be invariant under $t \rightarrow -t$ in the complex-conjugate Schrödinger equation. This leads to another set of solutions with eigenwavenumbers $k_{-n} = \alpha_{-n} + i\beta_{-n} = -\alpha_n + i\beta_n = (-k_n)^*$. These solutions will clearly be found in the third quadrant of the complex k plane, and we identify them as the *antiresonances*. The resonant eigenfunctions $\psi_n(x)$ obey the asymptotic relation

$$\psi_n(x) \sim e^{i\alpha_n x} e^{-\beta_n x}, \quad x \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.7)$$

The antiresonant eigenfunctions $\psi_{-n}(x) = \psi_n^*(x)$ obey

$$\psi_{-n}(x) \sim e^{-i\alpha_n x} e^{-\beta_n x}, \quad x \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.8)$$

Neither the resonant nor antiresonant states obey the usual orthonormality relations (see [More and Gerjuoy, 1973; Madrid and Gadella, 2002; Garcia-Calderon and Villavicencio, 2019]), *i.e.* it is not simply true that

$$\langle \psi_n | \psi_m \rangle = \delta_{mn}. \quad (2.9)$$

The bound and antibound states, as discussed in Chapter 1, are the special cases corresponding to $\alpha_n = 0$, resulting in the real, negative energies $\mathcal{E}_n = E_n = -\beta_n^2 < 0$. The bound states are those which have $\beta_n > 0$, whose coordinate wavefunctions $\psi_n(x)$ vanish sufficiently quickly beyond the range of the potential, and the antibound states have $\beta_n < 0$ and grow without bound as $|x| \rightarrow \infty$.

The resonant and antiresonant states are eigenfunctions of the Schrödinger equation which have complex energy eigenvalues that obey the asymptotic conditions given in Eqs. (2.4), (2.7) and (2.8) (see [Madrid and Gadella, 2002; Garcia-Calderon and Villavicencio, 2019; Ahmed et al., 2015; Zavin and Moiseyev, 2004] for details). Resonances can also be conceptualised as poles of the S Matrix, or equivalently as poles of the outgoing Green's function.

The central purpose of this chapter is to demonstrate the evolution in the complex plane of resonances and antiresonances, and to show how these states annihilate and form bound/antibound states. Interesting 'dynamical' structure appears here, such as the emergence of attractors for the trajectories of the states. The obvious place to start is to explore these trajectories, henceforth referred to as *flows*, in the complex k plane. Technically, we use the ka plane to work with a dimensionless quantity, but recall that $a = 1$. We will show that an alternative complex *potentiodynamic* plane, which incorporates the potential depth itself into the coordinates, is another useful space in which to explore these trajectories, as it elucidates the asymptotic behaviour of the states as the potential becomes infinite. We begin with this one-dimensional case because there will be no need to involve the use of special functions that will arise in the more complicated examples considered in later chapters.

2.2 Finding the resonances

To locate the states of interest, we must solve the eigenproblem in Eq. (2.5), which has general solution

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(x) &= A \exp(ikx) + B \exp(-ikx), & x < -a, \\ \psi(x) &= F \cos(\kappa x) + G \sin(\kappa x), & -a < x < a, \\ \psi(x) &= C \exp(ikx) + D \exp(-ikx), & x > a.\end{aligned}\tag{2.10}$$

Imposing the asymptotic conditions, we require $A = D = 0$. The continuity of the logarithmic derivative at the boundaries leads, after trivial algebra to

$$2k\kappa \cos(2\kappa a) - i(k^2 + \kappa^2) \sin(2\kappa a) = 0.\tag{2.11}$$

We refer to Eq. (2.11) as the *resonance condition*. We are interested in solutions of this equation which are $k_n \in \mathbb{C}$. This is a complex transcendental equation, which is why the discussion of reliable root finding methods in Chapter 1 was necessary. It is clear that Eq. (2.11) can also be written as

$$\tan(2\kappa a) + i \frac{2(ka)(\kappa a)}{(ka)^2 + (\kappa a)^2} = 0,\tag{2.12}$$

which, after using the identity

$$\tan 2\theta = \frac{2 \tan \theta}{1 - \tan^2 \theta},\tag{2.13}$$

can be written in factored form as

$$\left[\tan \kappa a + i \frac{ka}{\kappa a} \right] \left[\tan \kappa a + i \frac{\kappa a}{ka} \right] = 0.\tag{2.14}$$

This form allows us to group the states resulting from the first factor as the even (symmetric) states, and those from the second factor as the odd (antisymmetric) ones (Bransden and Joachain, 2000). Since $V(x) = V(-x)$ for this potential, the eigenstates can be constructed as a linear combination of a symmetric and antisymmetric contribution. For the resonant and antiresonant states which have $A = D = 0$, the symmetric states are given by

$$\psi_{\pm n}^s(x) = \begin{cases} \exp(-ik_{\pm n}x), & x < -a, \\ F \cos(\kappa_{\pm n}x), & -a < x < a, \\ \exp(ik_{\pm n}x), & x > a, \end{cases} \quad (2.15)$$

where, as noted, $k_{\pm n}$ are roots corresponding to the first factor of Eq. (2.14). Similarly, the antisymmetric resonant and antiresonant states are given by

$$\psi_{\pm n}^a(x) = \begin{cases} \exp(-ik_{\pm n}x), & x < -a, \\ G \sin(\kappa_{\pm n}x), & -a < x < a, \\ -\exp(ik_{\pm n}x), & x > a, \end{cases} \quad (2.16)$$

where the resonant wavenumbers $k_{\pm n}$ are from the second factor in Eq. (2.14).

The bound states are captured by this description too, as these correspond to wavenumbers $k_n = \beta_n > 0$, and $\mathcal{E}_n = E_n = -\beta_n^2 > -V_0$, so $\kappa = \sqrt{k^2 + V_0}$ is real and positive. This reduces Eq. (2.14) to the well established conditions for even and odd bound states

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa a \tan(\kappa a) &= \beta a, \\ \kappa a \cot(\kappa a) &= -\beta a. \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

Applying the root finding procedures of Chapter 1 to the transcendental resonance condition, Eq. (2.11), with $V_0 = 10$ as a representative value, results in Fig. (2.2). The

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.2: Solutions in the $k \in \mathbb{C}$ plane for $V_0 = 10$ showing: (a) Crossing of real {imaginary} zero contour levels in blue {orange}, with solutions shown as red dots. (b) Domain colouring plot as extra confirmation of the zeros - note the cycling of the phase about each one.

probability densities, *i.e.* $|\psi(x)|^2$ for the three bound states, the antibound state, and the first two resonances shown in Fig. (2.2) are plotted along with the potential well, as an energy level diagram in Fig. (2.3). Notice that the antibound state resembles a bound state inside the potential, but exponentially diverges into the classically forbidden region. The resonances are positive energy states, and exist above the well. The threshold bound state exists just below the top of the well, and represents a nascent bound state.

2.3 S Matrix

Information about incoming and outgoing particles can be encoded in a mathematically simple way using the so called S-matrix. For the purposes of scattering, we are only concerned with what occurs outside of the well, and the relevant pieces of the wavefunction are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(x) &= A \exp(ikx) + B \exp(-ikx), & x < -a, \\ \psi(x) &= C \exp(ikx) + D \exp(-ikx), & x > a.\end{aligned}\tag{2.18}$$

Notice that A and D represent amplitudes of incoming particles from the left and right respectively, and similarly B and C represent outgoing amplitudes to the left and right. The S-matrix relates the ‘incoming’ amplitudes to the ‘outgoing’ amplitudes, as the outgoing components are a linear combination of the incoming components. This fact can be expressed neatly by the matrix relation

$$\begin{pmatrix} B \\ C \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} \\ s_{21} & s_{22} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ D \end{pmatrix}.\tag{2.19}$$

The matrix that facilitates this linear transformation is the S-matrix. To find the left scattering solution, *i.e.* what happens when particles are sent in from the left, we have

Figure 2.3: Energy level diagram for a square potential well of depth $V_0 = 10$, $a = 1$, showing probability densities for the three bound states (one is the threshold bound state just below the top of the well), an antibound state, and two resonances. Blue {red} represents even {odd} states. The probabilities have been qualitatively re-scaled to be visible on the diagram at one scale. The horizontal dotted lines represent the real energies of the states.

$D = 0$. Then

$$B = s_{11}A \Rightarrow \frac{B}{A} = s_{11} = r_L, \quad (2.20)$$

where we have used the definition of the reflected amplitude to identify the first matrix element. Likewise for the transmission amplitude, we have

$$C = s_{21}A \Rightarrow \frac{C}{A} = s_{21} = t_R. \quad (2.21)$$

The same argument holds for the right scattering solution, but now with $A = 0$, and this results in $s_{12} = \frac{B}{D} = t_L$, and $s_{22} = \frac{C}{D} = r_R$. The S-matrix is then

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{pmatrix} r_L & t_R \\ t_L & r_R \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.22)$$

The probability must be conserved, so the outgoing and incoming probabilities must satisfy

$$|A|^2 + |D|^2 = |B|^2 + |C|^2. \quad (2.23)$$

This can be expressed more suggestively as

$$\begin{pmatrix} A^* & D^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B^* & C^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B \\ C \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.24)$$

Using the fact that with the S-matrix,

$$\begin{pmatrix} B \\ C \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{S} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ D \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.25)$$

we form the Hermitian conjugate

$$\begin{pmatrix} B^* & C^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A^* & D^* \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}^\dagger. \quad (2.26)$$

Using Eqs. (2.25) and (2.26) in Eq. (2.23), we have

$$\begin{pmatrix} A^* & D^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A^* & D^* \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}^\dagger \mathbf{S} \begin{pmatrix} A \\ D \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.27)$$

Clearly then, $\mathbf{S}^\dagger \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{I}$, meaning \mathbf{S} is a *unitary* matrix. For time-reversal invariant potentials, and in particular for the square well case considered in this chapter,

$$\begin{pmatrix} A^* \\ D^* \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{S} \begin{pmatrix} B^* \\ C^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.28)$$

But inverting Eq. (2.25) tells us that

$$\begin{pmatrix} A^* \\ D^* \end{pmatrix} = (\mathbf{S}^{-1})^* \begin{pmatrix} B^* \\ C^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.29)$$

Clearly $\mathbf{S} = (\mathbf{S}^{-1})^*$. By the unitarity of \mathbf{S} , we know $(\mathbf{S}^\mathbf{T})^* = \mathbf{S}^{-1}$, and it follows that $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{S}^\mathbf{T}$. The mirror symmetry of the potential confers symmetry to the S-matrix, and we know that $t_L = t_R = t$. After imposing the continuity conditions, and a lot of trivial algebra (Gasiorowicz, 2003), the matrix elements are found as

$$\begin{aligned} r_L = r_R &= \frac{-i(k^2 - \kappa^2) \sin(2\kappa a)}{2k\kappa \cos(2\kappa a) - i(k^2 + \kappa^2) \sin(2\kappa a)}, \\ t &= \frac{2k\kappa}{2k\kappa \cos(2\kappa a) - i(k^2 + \kappa^2) \sin(2\kappa a)}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.30)$$

As can be seen, the poles of these matrix elements occur for zeros of the denominator, which is precisely Eq. (2.11). To see how bound states relate to this, we analytically continue the S-matrix to negative energies, in which case $k \rightarrow i\beta$, and in order to have normalisable wavefunctions, $A = D = 0$ becomes a necessary condition. This leads to the relationship

$$\mathbf{S} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B \\ C \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.31)$$

Figure 2.4: Absolute value of an S-matrix element plotted over the $k \in \mathbb{C}$ plane for a square well with $V_0 = 10$ and $a = 1$. As poles become dense on the imaginary axis the structure is difficult to resolve in this region.

Clearly, this will be trivially satisfied when $(B \ C)^T = \mathbf{0}$, but this solution is not interesting. The other way for this to hold is if S-matrix elements diverge for particular energy values, *i.e.* when the S-matrix has poles. This result is quite wonderful because it shows how knowledge of only the scattering completely specifies the bound state energy spectrum. As a bonus, we also get resonances if we allow complex energies.

Considering again the representative values $V_0 = 10$ and $a = 1$, we can plot the absolute value of the S-matrix elements over the complex k plane. The result of this is shown in Fig.(2.4). A comparison of the zeros of the resonance condition and poles of the S-matrix is shown in Fig.(2.5).

Figure 2.5: Comparison of S-matrix poles [bottom] and resonance condition zeros [right] for a square well with $a = 1$, $V_0 = 10$.

2.4 Flows for the square well

We now turn our attention to the evolution of these states in two complex planes as the potential depth is varied, *i.e.* the flows of the states. We numerically solve the transcendental resonance condition given in Eq. (2.11) for a fixed value of potential parameters for resonant wavenumbers, k , and we follow the trajectories of each state as we incrementally vary the potential strength. The collection of all flows we refer to as a *flow portrait*. We use the complex wavenumber plane to follow the flows, as is traditional, but we also introduce a new *potentiodynamic* complex κa plane that includes the potential strength as an intrinsic feature of the coordinates. This new way of viewing the flows is useful in that flows that are unbounded in the ka plane often become bounded in the κa plane, and bound state flows do not overlap as they do in wavenumber coordinates, as we will demonstrate. The κa plane for the square well potential is described by

$$\kappa a = \sqrt{k^2 + V_0 a}. \quad (2.32)$$

Since the square root function is double-valued, we have two choices for how to define our potentiodynamic coordinate system. We opt to select the Riemann sheet for which $\kappa a \rightarrow ka$ as $V_0 \rightarrow 0$ as the most natural choice. We begin by considering shallow wells with $V_0 = 0.1$ and $V_0 = 0.5$ respectively, and fix $a = 1$. The positions of the states in the ka plane are shown in Fig. (2.6), and all four types of state are present. Analysing the flow trajectories will allow us to establish how scattering states become bound states *via* an attractor in the terminology of dynamical systems theory. Since there is always one bound state (and one antibound state) for arbitrarily shallow square wells, as shown in Fig. (2.6), we first trace the flows of these progenitor states as the potential well is deepened, and as shown in Figs. (2.7, 2.8), we observe that the ground state moves up along the positive imaginary axis in the ka plane and a new bound state is created as the progenitor antibound state crosses the origin. The asymptotic behaviour of the progenitor ground state for infinitesimally shallow and infinitely deep wells in the ka

Figure 2.6: Locations in the ka plane of the states for a square well of width $2a$ at two shallow potential values.

Figure 2.7: Flows of the progenitor antibound state in the ka plane as V_0 is increased beginning with the case of a potential of effectively zero depth. The trajectory of the progenitor bound state (the ground state) flows from $(0, 0)$ to $(0, i\infty)$. The flow of the progenitor antibound state starts at $(0, -i\infty)$ and flows to $(0, i\infty)$, becoming the first excited bound state as it crosses the origin. The flows have been artificially offset slightly for visibility.

Figure 2.8: Flows of the progenitor antibound state in the κa plane as V_0 is increased beginning with the case of a potential of effectively zero depth. The trajectory of the progenitor bound state (the ground state) flows from $(0, 0)$ and asymptotically approaches $(0, \pi/2)$. The flow of the progenitor antibound state starts at $(0, -i\infty)$ and moves along the negative imaginary axis, turns onto the positive real axis and asymptotically approaches $(\pi, 0)$, becoming the first excited bound state at $(\pi/2, 0)$. Limit points of flows in κa coordinates are shown as crosses. The flows have been slightly offset from each other for visibility.

plane are respectively described by

$$k_g a \rightarrow 0, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad k_g a \rightarrow i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.33)$$

The asymptotics of the progenitor antibound state follow

$$k_a a \rightarrow -i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad k_a a \rightarrow i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.34)$$

In the potentiodynamic κa plane, one can see in Fig. (2.8) that the progenitor bound state flows from the origin to the limit point $\pi/2$, *i.e.*

$$\kappa_g a \rightarrow 0, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad \kappa_g a \rightarrow \pi/2, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty, \quad (2.35)$$

so a flow that is unbounded in the usual ka coordinates becomes bounded in the new coordinate system. Antibound states in κa coordinates flow up the negative imaginary axis and turn onto the positive real axis at the origin (where $ka = -i$) to their limit points. For instance, the progenitor antibound state flows along the imaginary axis, onto the real axis, crosses $\pi/2$ (where $ka = 0$) where it becomes the first excited bound state, and then approaches the limit point π , *i.e.*

$$\kappa_a a \rightarrow -i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad \kappa_a a \rightarrow \pi, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.36)$$

The first two bound states are therefore somewhat special in that the ground state always exists and that the first excited state originates from an antibound state that always exists. All higher excited states arise from the annihilation of a pair of a resonance/antiresonance flows as they coalesce at the *attractor* located at $ka = -i$, as shown in Fig. (2.9). We index the resonant wavenumbers with increasing distance from the imaginary axis *i.e.* such that $|\operatorname{Re} k_{\pm 1}| < |\operatorname{Re} k_{\pm 2}| < \dots < |\operatorname{Re} k_{\pm m}| < \dots$. In the

Figure 2.9: Coalescence of the first two resonance and antiresonance pairs at the attractor $ka = -i$ to eventually create new bound states (and antibound states). The flows have been offset from the vertical axis to show that there are two in this area.

quantum opening limit, the resonance wavenumbers k_m obey

$$k_{\pm m}a \rightarrow \pm m\pi/2 - i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.37)$$

As the well depth is increased, the resonance and antiresonance pair annihilate at the attractor to produce two antibound states. One of these new antibound states remains antibound and moves down the imaginary axis of the ka plane towards $-i\infty$. The other moves up the imaginary axis, crossing to positive imaginary values and creating the next excited bound state. None of these flows remain bounded in the ka plane, which is where the potentiodynamic plane shows its utility.

In the κa coordinates, the starting values of the flows in the opening limit are the same since we have defined the potentiodynamic plane such that $\kappa a \rightarrow ka$ as $V_0 \rightarrow 0$. Therefore

$$\kappa_{\pm m}a \rightarrow \pm m\pi/2 - i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots \quad (2.38)$$

Figure 2.10: Trajectories of the first two resonance flows for the square well κa plane. The limit points are shown as crosses at $(3\pi/2, 0)$ and $(2\pi, 0)$. The attractors of antiresonance flows are located at $(-\pi/2, 0)$ and $(-\pi, 0)$.

Each of the resonances join the real axis at the real solutions of

$$\left(\tan(\kappa a) + \frac{1}{\kappa a} \right) (\tan(\kappa a) - \kappa a) = 0, \quad (2.39)$$

where we have used the fact that $ka = -i$ at the attractor in Eq. (2.14). The antibound state created by the m -th antiresonance flows to $\kappa a = -m\pi/2$, *i.e.*

$$\kappa a \rightarrow -m\pi/2, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.40)$$

The antibound state created from annihilation of the m -th resonance becomes an excited bound state after crossing $\kappa a = (m+1)\pi/2$, after which it asymptotically approaches $(m+2)\pi/2$ along the real axis, *i.e.*

$$\kappa_m a \rightarrow (m+2)\frac{\pi}{2}, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty. \quad (2.41)$$

These features are all presented in Fig. (2.10). It is clear that transforming solutions

into the new potentiodynamic plane has the effect of bounding all flows in the infinite well limit. The limit points are integer multiples of $\pi/2$. This bounding of flows for potentials of all depths suggests that this coordinate system is useful for understanding the asymptotic behaviours of the flows, as well as for separating out the excited state flows that all overlap in the ka plane. Further, it shows that this coordinate system is useful for relating the finite well to the infinite well, and may be useful for pedagogical purposes. We will discover that the potentiodynamic plane has extra utility for the more complicated potentials studied later in this work.

2.5 Flows for the square barrier

For completeness, we discuss the flows of the square barrier potential, which is a repulsive analogue of the square well. It is actually simpler to interpret these barriers, as they cannot support bound states, meaning that we only need to keep track of resonances, antiresonances, and antibound states. The potential itself is described by

$$V(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & |x| > a, \\ V_0, & |x| < a, \quad V_0 > 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.42)$$

Locating the resonances can be done from first principles, as for the square well, but it is simpler to analytically continue the expression for the square well resonance condition by changing the sign of V_0 . In accordance with this, we redefine

$$\kappa = \sqrt{k^2 - V_0}, \quad V_0 > 0. \quad (2.43)$$

Now the resonances are described by Eq. (2.11) with κ defined as above.

Following the previous strategy, we take a low barrier of effectively zero height, and solve Eq. (2.11) numerically using the strategies discussed in the introduction. We then

Figure 2.11: Flow portrait for resonances in the ka plane, showing the repeller at $ka = -i$.

trace out the flows of the states in both ka and κa coordinates as before. The flows in the ka plane are shown in Fig. (2.11), which shows that there initially exist two antibound states, one of which is near the origin, and one of which is below what is now a repeller at $ka = -i$. As V_0 is increased, these flows move towards the repeller, where they annihilate to produce a single resonance/antiresonance pair. These special antibound states respectively obey

$$k_{\pm 1}a \rightarrow 0 \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad k_{\pm 1}a \rightarrow -i\infty \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.44)$$

All other ($k_{\pm m}, m \neq 1$) resonances/antiresonances obey

$$k_{\pm m}a \rightarrow \pm(m-1)\frac{\pi}{2} - i\infty, \quad V_0 \rightarrow 0, \quad m = 2, 3, \dots \quad (2.45)$$

As the barrier height increases, the resonances move up to the right, and antiresonances move up to the left. None of these flows intersect or join. The asymptotic behaviour of

Figure 2.12: Flow portrait for resonances in the κa plane, with limit points of the flows shown at crosses at $(m\pi/2, 0)$ for resonances and $(-m\pi/2, 0)$ for antiresonances.

the flows is described by

$$k_{\pm m}a \rightarrow \pm\infty - 0i, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty, \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (2.46)$$

This shows that no resonances exist for the infinite (impenetrable) barrier, as one would expect.

The story in the κa plane is shown in Fig. (2.12). Here again, we observe annihilation of the two original antibound states to produce the ‘special’ resonance/antiresonance pair, and we see that these flows, and all other flows not created from antibound states have limit points on the real axis at $(m\pi/2, 0)$ for resonance flows and $(-m\pi/2, 0)$ for antiresonance flows. That is

$$\kappa_{\pm m}a \rightarrow \pm m\frac{\pi}{2}, \quad V_0 \rightarrow \infty, \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (2.47)$$

2.6 Summary

In this chapter, we studied the one dimensional square well/barrier system. The results here are well established, but we introduced and tested the potentiodynamic coordinate system, which is a useful new way of interpreting flow portraits which is obvious in hindsight but did not appear explicitly in any of the literature as far as we could find. The successful recapitulation of accepted 1D results shows that our numerical procedures are functioning as expected, and we are well equipped to push this type of analysis into uncharted territory with the 2D potentials.

The fact that attractors and repellers appear as features in such a simple potential system is highly suggestive that we should expect very rich structure to appear for more elaborate potentials.

Chapter 3

Two Dimensional Circular Barrier

Now that we have established that the numerical procedures function properly, and have shown interesting dynamical behaviour in one dimensional systems, we will step up the complexity and study two dimensional, rotationally symmetric potentials. Firstly, in this chapter, we study a cylindrical barrier. Next we will consider a well. In so doing, we will see that Bessel and Hankel functions emerge, making good numerical procedures even more necessary to obtain a clear picture of what is happening. The results of this chapter have been published in *Physica E* (Meeten and Morozov, 2020b).

3.1 Circular barrier potential

We define the potential system of interest as a repulsive barrier, of circular cross section with radius R , and height V_0 . That is

$$V(r) = \begin{cases} V_0, & r < R, \\ 0, & r > R. \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Working again in Rydberg units, the time-independent Schrödinger equation can be written as

$$[-\nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r})] \psi(\mathbf{r}) = \mathcal{E}\psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3.2)$$

Noting that $V(\mathbf{r}) = V(r) = V_0$, and rewriting the equation as a pair of Helmholtz equations, we have

$$\begin{aligned} [\nabla^2 + k^2] \psi(\mathbf{r}) &= 0, & k &= \sqrt{\mathcal{E}}, & r &> R, \\ [\nabla^2 + \kappa^2] \psi(\mathbf{r}) &= 0, & \kappa &= \sqrt{k^2 - V_0}, & r &< R. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Since the potential of interest has circular symmetry, it is natural to utilise a polar coordinate system, (r, φ) . The Laplacian in polar coordinates is (Arfken, 2012)

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \varphi^2}. \quad (3.4)$$

Recasting the Helmholtz equations in polar coordinates leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \varphi^2} + k^2 \psi(r, \varphi) &= 0, & r &> R, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \varphi^2} + \kappa^2 \psi(r, \varphi) &= 0, & r &< R. \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

We then attempt a separation of variables ansatz of the form $\psi(r, \varphi) = R(r)\Phi(\varphi)$, and substitute this into the polar coordinate Helmholtz equation. For the $r > R$ equation, this proceeds as

$$\Phi(\varphi) \frac{\partial^2 R(r)}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\Phi(\varphi)}{r} \frac{\partial R(r)}{\partial r} + \frac{R(r)}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\varphi)}{\partial \varphi^2} + k^2 R(r)\Phi(\varphi) = 0. \quad (3.6)$$

Dividing through by $\psi(r, \varphi) = R(r)\Phi(\varphi)$ yields

$$\frac{1}{R(r)} \frac{\partial^2 R(r)}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{rR(r)} \frac{\partial R(r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2\Phi(\varphi)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\varphi)}{\partial \varphi^2} + k^2 = 0. \quad (3.7)$$

Now, multiplying through by r^2 and separating the r and φ dependencies on either side, we can write

$$\frac{r^2}{R(r)} \frac{\partial^2 R(r)}{\partial r^2} + \frac{r}{R(r)} \frac{\partial R(r)}{\partial r} + r^2 k^2 = -\frac{1}{\Phi(\varphi)} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(\varphi)}{\partial \varphi^2}. \quad (3.8)$$

For both equations to be true $\forall r, \varphi$ both sides must be equal to a separation constant, μ . The simpler of the equations is the angular one. This becomes

$$\frac{d^2 \Phi(\varphi)}{d\varphi^2} + \mu \Phi(\varphi) = 0. \quad (3.9)$$

The eigenfunctions of Eq. (3.9) are trivial, and are sinusoids (or complex exponentials) of the form

$$\Phi(\varphi) = \begin{cases} \cos(\sqrt{\mu}\varphi), \\ \sin(\sqrt{\mu}\varphi). \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

The solutions are only physically reasonable when they are periodic in the well. We require $\Phi(\varphi) = \Phi(\varphi + 2\pi)$. This imposes the restriction that $\sqrt{\mu} = m \in \mathbb{Z}$. Hence we have the angular eigenfunctions

$$\Phi_m(\varphi) = \begin{cases} \cos(m\varphi), \\ \sin(m\varphi), \end{cases} \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (3.11)$$

Returning to Eq. (3.8), we consider the radial part. That is, with $\mu = m^2$,

$$\frac{r^2}{R(r)} \frac{d^2 R(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{r}{R(r)} \frac{dR(r)}{dr} + r^2 k^2 = m^2. \quad (3.12)$$

This can be written as

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + r \frac{dR}{dr} + (r^2 k^2 - m^2) R(r) = 0. \quad (3.13)$$

Eq. (3.13) is a modified version of the Bessel equation. Consulting Bowman (Bowman, 1958), we observe that an equation of the form

$$x^2 \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + (2p + 1)x \frac{dy}{dx} + (\alpha^2 x^{2s} + \beta^2)y = 0 \quad (3.14)$$

has general solution

$$y = x^{-p} \left[C_1 J_{q/s} \left(\frac{\alpha}{s} x^s \right) + C_2 Y_{q/s} \left(\frac{\alpha}{s} x^s \right) \right], \quad (3.15)$$

where $q \equiv \sqrt{p^2 - \beta^2}$, and C_1 and C_2 are constants. In Eq. (3.15), the functions $J_{q/s}$ and $Y_{q/s}$ are respectively known as Bessel functions of the first and second kinds. In this case these functions are both of order q/s .

Comparing Eqs. (3.13) and (3.14), we see that if $p = 0$, $\alpha = k$, $s = 1$, and $\beta^2 = -m^2$. This means $q = m$. The general solution of the radial equation (3.13) is therefore

$$R(r) = C_1 J_m(kr) + C_2 Y_m(kr). \quad (3.16)$$

There is a strong analogy between Eq. (3.16) and 1D solutions in the trigonometric basis, *i.e.* $F \cos(kx) + G \sin(kx)$. Indeed, just as $\cos(kx) \pm i \sin(kx) = e^{\pm i k x}$, analogous relationships exist between Bessel functions of the first kind and second kinds, *i.e.* $J_m(kr)$ and $Y_m(kr)$ respectively. The relationships are

$$\begin{aligned} H_m^{(1)}(kr) &= J_m(kr) + i Y_m(kr), \\ H_m^{(2)}(kr) &= J_m(kr) - i Y_m(kr). \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

These are known as Hankel functions of the first kind and second kinds in accordance with the bracketed superscript. In 1D, we often prefer to use the trigonometric representation of the solutions of the Schrödinger equation within the range of the potential, and the complex exponential representation beyond this range, in the free particle region. We opt to take this analogy seriously in the 2D case. The radial solution can

then be written as

$$R(r) = \begin{cases} A J_m(\kappa r) + B Y_m(\kappa r), & r < R, \\ C H_m^{(1)}(kr) + D H_m^{(2)}(kr), & r > R. \end{cases}$$

Two physical facts allow us to simplify this further. Firstly, Bessel functions of the second kind, $Y_m(\kappa r)$ are singular at $r = 0$, so we reject these immediately by setting $B = 0$ in order to have a physically meaningful solution. Additionally, for resonances we are interested in the outgoing solution far from the potential, and we impose the outgoing asymptotic condition

$$R(r) \sim \frac{\exp(ikr)}{\sqrt{r}}, \quad r \rightarrow \infty. \quad (3.18)$$

This banishes the Hankel function of the second kind from our solution ($D = 0$), as these physically represent *incoming* cylindrical waves. The Hankel functions of the first kind are exactly what we need, as these physically represent *outgoing* cylindrical waves, and obey the asymptotic condition Eq. (3.18). Hence, the radial solution is reduced to

$$R_m(r) = \begin{cases} N_m J_m(\kappa r), & r < R, \\ H_m^{(1)}(kr), & r > R, \end{cases}$$

where we supply the index m to illustrate that the quantisation from the angular equations resultantly manifests itself here in the radial case. The coefficient N_m is a normalisation constant to ensure continuity at the boundary $r = R$ for each m .

The full coordinate wavefunctions are then given by

$$\psi_m(r, \varphi) = \begin{cases} N_m J_m(\kappa r) \begin{pmatrix} \cos(m\varphi) \\ \sin(m\varphi) \end{pmatrix}, & r < R, \\ H_m^{(1)}(kr) \begin{pmatrix} \cos(m\varphi) \\ \sin(m\varphi) \end{pmatrix}, & r > R. \end{cases}$$

3.2 Resonances

Imposing continuity of the wavefunction $\psi_m(r, \varphi)$ and its normal derivative along the boundary $r = R$, we establish the conditions

$$\begin{aligned} N_m J_m(\kappa R) - H_m^{(1)}(kR) &= 0, \\ \kappa N_m \left. \frac{\partial J_m(\kappa r)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} - k \left. \frac{\partial H_m^{(1)}(kr)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

Dividing the former of Eqs. (3.19) by the latter and rearranging yields a transcendental condition for resonances

$$kJ_m(\kappa R) \left. \frac{\partial H_m^{(1)}(kr)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} - \kappa H_m^{(1)}(kR) \left. \frac{\partial J_m(\kappa r)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} = 0. \quad (3.20)$$

This can be simplified further to eliminate the derivatives, which is advantageous for computational reasons. Referring again to Bowman (Bowman, 1958) we observe the identity

$$\frac{\partial Z_m(kr)}{\partial r} \equiv \frac{mZ_m(kr)}{kr} - Z_{m+1}(kr), \quad (3.21)$$

where Z can be Bessel or Hankel functions. Using this identity in Eq. (3.20), we obtain

$$kJ_m(\kappa R) \left[\frac{mH_m^{(1)}(kR)}{kR} - H_{m+1}(kR) \right] - \kappa H_m^{(1)}(kR) \left[\frac{mJ_m(\kappa R)}{\kappa R} - J_{m+1}(\kappa R) \right] = 0, \quad (3.22)$$

which simplifies to

$$kJ_m(\kappa R)H_{m+1}^{(1)}(kR) - \kappa J_{m+1}(\kappa R)H_m^{(1)}(kR) = 0. \quad (3.23)$$

We then utilise the numerical methods described in Chapter 1 to find the solutions $k \in \mathbb{C}$ of Eq. (3.23). Each different value of m will be treated as a separate case. As an illustration of the methods applied to this system, we set $R = 1$ and $V_0 = 10$ with $m = 2$. This potential cannot support bound states, and as such we are only interested in the solutions in quadrant 4 of the kR plane. The output of the root finding algorithm is shown in Fig. (3.1). For each m , there is a zero which appears on the positive real axis at exactly $k = \sqrt{V_0}$. This is a solution of Eq. (3.23) but is *not* a solution of the original system Eq. (3.19). We therefore refer to such extra solutions as *parasitic*, and they are filtered out of the numerical routines.

An energy level diagram featuring the probability densities of the three resonances visible in Fig. (3.1) is shown in Fig. (3.2). Note that a new feature is present in two dimensions that does not manifest in the one dimensional systems of Chapter 2. This is the appearance of two different classes of resonance. Resonances of the first class are known as *external* (or *shape*) resonances, (Dubertrand et al., 2008) because reference to Fig. (3.2) shows that the probability density lies completely beyond the range of the potential. It is also interesting to note that its energy is below the barrier height. Resonances in the second class are known as *internal* resonances, because they have significant density on the range $r < R$, *inside* the potential. They also exist completely above the barrier in terms of energy. There are infinitely many internal resonances for any given m , but finitely many external resonances, whose quantity is given by the integer part of $m/2$. Both internal and external resonances also arise in the context of

optical problems, and the interested reader should refer to (Cho et al., 2010, 2011; Cao and Wiersig, 2015) for a treatment in the context of dielectric cavities.

3.3 Flows and probability densities

When we study the flows of the resonances, we will observe dramatic differences in the asymptotic behaviours of internal and external resonances, which lends a pleasing duality to the trajectories in the kR and κR coordinate systems.

We begin the discussion of resonant flows by considering a circular barrier of near zero height, solving the resonance condition Eq. (3.23) using the numerical procedures discussed in Chapter 1. We then elucidate the dynamical behaviour of the resonances as the barrier is raised incrementally by following the position of each resonance in the kR plane throughout this procedure. Flow portraits for the cases $m = 0, 3, 4$ are considered here in order to give clear examples of the special case $m = 0$ and an even and odd value of m . We note that analogous patterns exist for all other $m > 0$. The flow portraits are shown in Figs. (3.3 - 3.5). The resonances in these figures are naturally separated into two categories in accordance with the character of their flows. In the kR plane, (upper panels of the figures) we describe resonances whose flows asymptotically approach zeros of Hankel functions of the first kind of order m as *external* resonances, and resonances whose flows do not converge to a limit point as *internal* resonances. It seems therefore, that the 2D case is more rich than the 1D case studied in Chapter 2, because here we see the possible emergence of more than one attractor in the kR plane depending on m . The number of external resonances is given by $(m - 1)/2$ for odd m and $m/2$ for even m . We index the external resonances in order of increasing real part with the index $q_e \in \{1, \dots, Q\}$, where Q is the number of Hankel function zeros in quadrant 4 of the kR plane. Notice therefore that there are no external resonances for $m = 0, 1$ - a manifestation of the absence of Hankel function zeros for these cases.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.1: Resonances as solutions of Eq. (3.23) with $R = 1$, $V_0 = 10$, $m = 2$ in the $kR \in \mathbb{C}$ plane showing: (a) Crossing of real {imaginary} zero contour levels in blue {orange}, with solutions shown as red dots. (b) Domain colouring plot as extra confirmation of the zeros. Note the zero on the real axis, which is a *parasitic* root.

Figure 3.2: Energy level diagram for a cylindrical potential barrier of height $V_0 = 10$, $m = 2$, and radius $R = 1$, showing probability densities for the first three resonances. The lowest energy resonance is an external resonance, and the other two are internal resonances. The probabilities have been qualitatively re-scaled to be visible on the diagram at one scale.

The internal resonances are infinite in number, and asymptotically diverge to real infinity in the kR plane. We index these internal resonances in order of increasing real part with the radial modal index $q_i \in \{1, 2, \dots\}$.

To see the duality of the kR and κR planes, it can be seen from the lower panels of Figs. (3.3 - 3.5) that the flows that converge in the kR plane now diverge in the κR plane to $-i\infty$, and that divergent flows in the kR plane now converge to limit points in the κR plane. As such we see that the infinite number of internal resonance flows are now easier to describe in the potentiodynamic coordinates, because the q_i th internal resonance flow has a limit point which is the q_i th zero of the Bessel function of the first kind of order m . Both coordinate systems feature attracting points for one class of resonance flows, and this observation seems to indicate that while the kR plane is well suited for interpretation of external resonances, it is the potentiodynamic κR plane that furnishes us with a natural arena in which to examine the behaviour of internal resonances.

For completeness and to clarify our *internal* and *external* nomenclature, we display the probability density plots for resonant states for the representative cases of $m = 3$ and $m = 4$, all with barrier height $V_0 = 50$ in Figs. (3.6 - 3.9). These figures show the correct number of ‘hotspots’ for the appropriate value of m , namely that we expect $2m$ such spots in the azimuthal direction. The radial modal index q_i correctly describes the number of hotspots radially for internal resonances. Moreover, the external resonance states have densities which exist mostly outside the range of the potential, while the internal resonances have some probability density within the barrier.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.3: Flow portraits for $m = 0$. The top [bottom] panel shows the kR [κR] plane. The zeros of Bessel functions of the first kind are labelled j_{m,q_i} where m denotes the order and q_i the radial mode number.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.4: Flow portraits for $m = 3$. The top [bottom] panel shows the kR [κR] plane. The zeros of Bessel [Hankel] functions of the first kind are labelled j_{m,q_i} [h_{m,q_e}] where m denotes the order and q_i [q_e] the radial mode number for internal [external] resonances.

Figure 3.5: Flow portraits for $m = 4$. The top [bottom] panel shows the kR [κR] plane. The zeros of Bessel [Hankel] functions of the first kind are labelled j_{m,q_i} [h_{m,q_e}] where m denotes the order and q_i [q_e] the radial mode number for internal [external] resonances.

Figure 3.6: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential barrier with $V_0 = 50$ for the only external ($q_e = 1$) [left panel] and the first internal ($q_i = 1$) [right panel] resonance. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the barrier boundary.

Figure 3.7: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential barrier with $V_0 = 50$ for the second internal ($q_i = 2$) [left panel] and the third internal ($q_i = 3$) [right panel] resonance. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the barrier boundary.

Figure 3.8: Probability density plots for the case $m = 4$ for a potential barrier with $V_0 = 50$ for the two external resonances: $q_e = 1$ [left panel], $q_e = 2$ [right panel]. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the barrier boundary.

Figure 3.9: Probability density plots for the case $m = 4$ for a potential barrier with $V_0 = 50$ for the first internal ($q_i = 1$) [left panel] and the second internal ($q_i = 2$) [right panel] resonance. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the barrier boundary.

3.4 Summary

The 2D circular barrier potential exhibits richer resonance phenomena than the 1D systems of Chapter 2. We find that there are now two distinct types of resonance, each with its own type of flow behaviour and a suitable coordinate system in which it possesses limit points. We have set the stage here for the discussion of the circular well, which is much more complicated because there are bound states to consider.

Chapter 4

Two Dimensional Circular Well

In this chapter we study the more complicated case of an *attractive* two dimensional circular potential. The complications arise essentially because there are now bound states, meaning that there is an interplay between the types of states. We will see that we have to modify the definition of Hankel functions to ensure that time reversal invariance is preserved, and the entire story is complicated by the fact that there are multiple Riemann sheets involved in the analysis. Accordingly, the dynamical behaviour of the states is far richer than in the barrier case. Matters of degeneracy also become relevant which was not an issue in the 1D systems. A first pass of the results of this chapter were published in *Physical Review A* (Meeten et al., 2019).

4.1 Circular well potential

The potential of interest in this chapter is an attractive finite circular well, of radius R and depth V_0 described by

$$V(r) = \begin{cases} -V_0, & r < R, \\ 0, & r > R. \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

The infinite circular analogue is well studied - see for instance (Robinett, 1996; Robinett and Heppelmann, 2002). With the usual Rydberg units, the analysis proceeds in the same manner as in Chapter 3, to arrive at the same resonance condition with $\kappa = \sqrt{k^2 + V_0}$, namely

$$kJ_m(\kappa R)H_{m+1}^{(1)}(kR) - \kappa J_{m+1}(\kappa R)H_m^{(1)}(kR) = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

Finding the roots of this equation for a potential of depth $V_0 = 20$, radius $R = 1$, and $m = 2$ as an example gives Fig. (4.1). Examination of this figure reveals an immediate problem - the solutions do not obey $k_{-n} = (-k_n)^*$, that is to say they are not time reversal invariant. The reason for this lies in the fact that although Bessel functions are single-valued, Hankel functions are actually multi-valued, with a branch cut along the negative real axis, as can be seen in Fig. (4.2). The time reversal symmetric partners of the resonances are actually on a different Riemann sheet of the resonance condition, and since the only parts of the resonance condition that are multi-valued are the Hankel functions, we must adjust how we define Hankel functions in order to gain control of the sheet being accessed. The Hankel function has alternative representation (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1972; Gradshteyn and Ryzhik, 2007)

$$H_m^{(1)}(z) = J_m(z) + iS_m(z) + i\frac{2}{\pi}J_m(z) \log\left(\frac{z}{2}\right), \quad (4.3)$$

where $J_m(z)$ is the single-valued Bessel function and $S_m(z)$ is a polynomial, which is single-valued by construction. The function $S_m(z)$ can be written as

$$S_m(z) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \frac{(m-j-1)!}{j!} \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^{2j-m} - \frac{1}{\pi} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^j \frac{1}{j!(j+m)!} \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^{m+2j} \\ \times [F(j+1) + F(j+m+1)], \quad (4.4)$$

Figure 4.1: Roots of Eq. (4.2) with $V_0 = 20$, $m = 2$ and $R = 1$ in the $kR \in \mathbb{C}$ plane showing: [Left panel] Crossing of real {imaginary} zero contour levels in blue {orange}, with solutions shown as red dots. [Right panel] Domain colouring plot as extra confirmation of the zeros. Note the sharp change in phase on the negative real axis, indicating the presence of a branch cut.

Figure 4.2: Absolute value plots showing [left panel] Hankel function, $H_2(z)$ with branch cut on negative real axis and [right panel] single-valued Bessel function, $J_2(z)$.

where $F(z)$ is the so-called digamma function. This is defined to be the logarithmic derivative of $\Gamma(z)$, the gamma function, *i.e.*

$$F(z) = \frac{d \ln \Gamma(z)}{dz}. \quad (4.5)$$

Therefore, the only multi-valued part of the Hankel function in this representation is the logarithm. This is an elegant form, since the (principal) complex logarithm is defined as

$$\log z = \ln r + i\phi, \quad -\pi < \phi \leq \pi, \quad (4.6)$$

and accessing different branches of the complex logarithm is trivial, since all we need to do is use a different argument function.

We choose a different argument function $\tilde{\phi}$ to recover the time-reversal symmetry partners of the resonances. These are the antiresonances, which are reflections of the resonances in the negative imaginary axis. To do this, we opt to move the branch cut to the negative imaginary axis, see (Doost et al., 2013) for details. We define the new argument function as

$$\tilde{\phi} = \begin{cases} \phi, & -\pi/2 < \phi \leq \pi, \\ \phi + 2\pi, & -\pi < \phi \leq -\pi/2. \end{cases}$$

The new, *modified* Hankel function, which we denote by $\mathcal{H}_m(z)$ now has a branch cut on the negative imaginary axis, and agrees with the original Hankel function in quadrants 1, 2 and 4, with different values in the third quadrant. The required symmetry is now restored, *i.e.* we satisfy the condition

$$[\mathcal{H}_m(-z^*)]^* = \mathcal{H}_m(z). \quad (4.7)$$

We show the distribution of zeros for the original and modified Hankel functions for $m \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ in Fig. (4.3) (Cruz and Sesma, 1982; Kerimov and Skorokhodov, 1985;

Figure 4.3: Distribution of zeros of (a) $H_m(z)$, the original Hankel function and (b) $\mathcal{H}_m(z)$, the modified Hankel function in the z plane.

Figure 4.4: Roots of Eq. (4.8) with $V_0 = 20$, $m = 2$ and $R = 1$ in the $kR \in \mathbb{C}$ plane showing: [Left panel] Crossing of real {imaginary} zero contour levels in blue {orange}, with solutions shown as red dots. [Right panel] Domain colouring plot as extra confirmation of the zeros. Note the sharp change in phase has moved to the negative imaginary axis, and that the phase is continuous over the negative real axis, indicating the adjusted branch cut. The required time-reversal symmetry is now present.

Erdelyi, 1953). Now that the required symmetry has been reinstated, we reformulate the resonance condition using the modified Hankel function as

$$kJ_m(\kappa R)\mathcal{H}_{m+1}(kR) - \kappa J_{m+1}(\kappa R)\mathcal{H}_m(kR) = 0. \quad (4.8)$$

Applying our routines to Eq. (4.8) results in Fig. (4.4). Notice that the phase no longer abruptly changes over the negative real axis, but instead this now happens on the negative imaginary axis. This confirms that we have successfully adjusted the branch cut to the required position. The same phenomenon of parasitic solutions as discussed for the barrier case happens now for the well for $kR = \pm i\sqrt{V_0}$. Also note that the roots now satisfy $k_{-n} = (-k_n)^*$, as required. An energy level diagram showing the probability densities of bound states, an external resonance, and an internal resonance for a deep well of $V_0 = 70$, radius $R = 1$, and $m = 2$ is shown in Fig. (4.5).

Figure 4.5: Energy level diagram for a cylindrical potential well of depth $V_0 = 70$, $m = 2$, and radius $R = 1$, showing probability densities for the two bound states, the external resonance and the first internal resonance from bottom to top. The probabilities have been qualitatively re-scaled to be visible on the diagram at one scale.

4.2 Flows and probability densities

Now that we have access to the resonances and antiresonances of this potential, we can now incrementally vary the depth of the well to trace the interplay between the (anti)resonances and bound states. There are three cases for the distinct flow portraits that emerge from this process.

We first consider the case of an even value of the quantum number m . The results discussed are exemplified by both panels of Fig. (4.6). With the modified Hankel function discussed previously forming part of the resonance condition, the entire flow portrait for even m is immediately symmetric about the imaginary axis of the kR plane, as required by time-reversal symmetry. This is due to the symmetric distribution of adjusted Hankel function zeros. Each state present is doubly degenerate here, so all flows should be thought of as occurring in duplicate. Like with the circular barrier potential, one again observes the presence of the two distinct classes of resonance discussed in Chapter 3, however the flow behaviour of external resonances is now much more interesting than in the barrier case. The flow approaches the attracting Hankel function zero in a spiral fashion. The number of these spiral flows will be one less than the number of Hankel function zeros in the 4th quadrant of the kR plane, *i.e.* none for $m = 2$, which has 1 zero, and 1 for $m = 4$, which has 2. These cases are shown in the upper and lower panels of Fig. (4.6) respectively.

Perhaps even more interesting still is the flow behaviour of the internal resonances. We observe the apparent coalescence of each internal resonance and corresponding antiresonance partner at the origin of the kR plane. This occurs in tandem with the generation of a new bound state from the origin. Both flows join at zero and initially move down the imaginary axis splitting slightly to either side of the axis, before these flows split more dramatically into two, temporarily diverting from the axis in opposite directions as they pass close to the nearby attracting adjusted Hankel zeros $h_{m,1}$ and

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.6: Flow portraits in the kR plane for $m = 2$ [$m = 4$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. Hankel function zeros are labelled $h_{m,j}$, where $j \in \{1 \dots m/2\}$. All flows are doubly degenerate, and the thicker lines represent overlapping flows. Bound state flows have been offset from the imaginary axis for clarity.

$-h_{m,1}^*$. After a close encounter with the attractors, the flows recombine asymptotically and flow to $-i\infty$ together. We refer to the states after coalescence at the origin as ‘quasi antibound’ states, because a true antibound state would have exactly zero real part, while the states here still have an evanescent real part, which becomes temporarily substantial near the attractors close to the axis before diminishing again. Thus for (anti)resonance states, doubly degenerate antiresonance flows meet doubly degenerate resonance flows to produce a pair of doubly degenerate quasi antibound flows. It is an interesting observation that whenever these quasi antibound state flows begin to recombine, this seems to precipitate the generation of a new bound state. Thus there are two explanatory effects in the kR plane related to the creation of bound states. The first is the coalescence of the flows at the origin. A more subtle effect is the recombination of the quasi antibound state flows, which heralds the creation of all but the first bound state for each m . Each nascent bound state appears to spontaneously emerge from the origin in kR coordinates as a scattering state from the continuum becomes trapped by the potential. The bound states flow towards $i\infty$ as $V_0 \rightarrow -\infty$. Note that in Fig. (4.6), bound state flows on the positive imaginary axis have been horizontally offset from one another for clarity because the flows overlap here in the kR plane.

We observed in Chapter 2 that the κR complex plane had the useful effect of bounding and separating out the flows of bound states, whereas in the kR plane they overlap on the positive imaginary axis and diverge to $k = i\infty$. The same effect occurs here with some variations. The flow portraits in κR coordinates for $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ are shown in the upper and lower panels of Fig. (4.7) respectively. Here we see again the dual nature of the k and κ systems - bounded flows in kR coordinates become unbounded in potentiodynamic coordinates and *vice versa*. To see more details, we can follow the trajectory in Fig. (4.8) of the first internal resonance, $q_i = 1$ for $m = 2$. This doubly degenerate resonance flows towards attracting point $j_{1,1}$, the first zero of the Bessel function of the first kind of order 1. This point is also a generator for the

ground bound state in the κR plane. Meanwhile the resonance flow goes back into the 4th quadrant of the κR plane (we referred to this previously as a quasi antibound flow) and traces out a loop, approaching the real axis at a larger value and flows from right to left towards the first zero of the *next* Bessel function, $j_{2,1}$, converging on the limit point from slightly below the real axis. Simultaneously, the bound state moves along the real axis from left to right from $j_{1,1}$ to $j_{2,1}$. The same type of behaviour holds for each internal resonance, with the q_i th resonance flowing to the attractor at j_{m-1,q_i} . This point is also the generator for the q_i th bound state ($q_i = 1$ for the ground state, $q_i = 2$ for the first excited state *etc.*) which then flows to j_{m,q_i} as the potential is made infinitely deep. The origin of the kR plane is the generator for *all* bound states, but each doubly degenerate bound state has a unique generator in the κR plane. The quasi antibound part of the flow loops around in the fourth quadrant and then approaches the real axis, before flowing from right to left to j_{m,q_i} from slightly below the real axis. This is pleasing because the journey of every bound state, from its creation to its ultimate fate in the infinite well limit, inhabits distinct regions of the κR plane, partitioned by corresponding zeros of adjacent Bessel functions. In the third quadrant of the κR plane, the antiresonance flows are mirror images of the resonance flows in the fourth quadrant. The only difference here is that there are no flows on the real axis because there are no antibound states.

The case of even $m \neq 0$ is simple because only the principal branch of Eq. (4.8) was needed to account for all flows. For the odd m case this is no longer true. Consideration of only the principal branch of the resonance condition results in loss of state conservation when internal resonance and antiresonance flows coalesce. When this happens on the principal sheet, we appear to lose track of these states completely. It is only when we analyse the adjacent Riemann sheets - one above, and one below the principal sheet - that we find the missing solutions whose flows resemble the quasi antibound flows of the even case. We therefore augment our set of resonances with those states on adjacent sheets that are generated from the coalescence of internal flows at the origin.

Figure 4.7: Flow portraits in the κR plane for $m = 2$ [$m = 4$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. All flows are doubly degenerate. Bessel function zeros are labelled by j_{p,q_i} , where $p \in \{m - 1, m, \dots\}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.8: Zoomed in flow portraits in the κR plane for $m = 2$ [$m = 4$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. All flows are doubly degenerate. Bessel function zeros are labelled by j_{p,q_i} , where $p \in \{m-1, m, \dots\}$. Bound state flows occur between corresponding zeros of adjacent Bessel functions.

Again all flows for the odd case are doubly degenerate, including these new flows from the neighbouring sheets. The results for the odd case in the kR plane (exemplified by the particular cases $m = 1$ and $m = 3$) are shown in Fig. (4.9). With our augmented set of resonances, all the same patterns as in the even case hold in the kR and κR planes, as evidenced by Figs. (4.9 - 4.11). The simplest case is the case when $m = 0$, which has every state nondegenerate and features a permanent bound state. Referring to Fig. (4.12) we see that the mechanism by which bound states are generated has some similarities and some differences when compared to the $m \neq 0$ cases. Since there is always one permanent bound state, this state cannot be interpreted to arise from coalescence of resonance and antiresonance flows. Moreover, the origin of the kR plane is not an attracting point of any flows here, so one of the two effects proposed to predict the generation of bound states is not present in this case. The other effect, in which an internal resonance-antiresonance pair flow together and combine asymptotically to prompt the spontaneous emergence of a bound state from the generator at the origin does feature here. Since there are no Hankel function zeros for $m = 0$, we do not observe any spiral orbits or temporary peeling apart of flows that occurs in other cases. This is further evidence that the Hankel function zeros are really driving the dynamics of the states in the kR plane.

In the κR plane, the story for $m = 0$ is correspondingly unique - there are no loops between zeros of Bessel functions and instead we see the simpler picture of bound states being separated into the usual regions between Bessel function zeros. We also note the flows of bound states and corresponding quasi antibound states converging from opposite sides to each Bessel function zero.

Probability density plots of the eigensolutions corresponding to the resonant states were plotted in Figs. (4.13 - 4.16), revealing the characteristic pattern of whispering gallery mode resonances. Like in the circular barrier case, there are $2m$ hotspots in the azimuthal direction and increasing numbers of hotspots radially as determined by q_i , the radial modal index. The representative case $m = 3$ was chosen to illustrate how the

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.9: Flow portraits in the kR plane for $m = 1$ [$m = 3$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. Hankel function zeros are labelled $h_{m,j}$, where $j \in \{1 \dots (m-1)/2\}$, and $h_{m,z}$ lies on an adjacent Riemann sheet. All flows are doubly degenerate, and the thicker lines represent overlapping flows. Bound state flows have been offset from the imaginary axis for clarity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.10: Flow portraits in the κR plane for $m = 1$ [$m = 3$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. All flows are doubly degenerate. Bessel function zeros are labelled by j_{p,q_i} , where $p \in \{m - 1, m, \dots\}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.11: Zoomed in flow portraits in the κR plane for $m = 1$ [$m = 3$] in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i (q_e) enumerate internal (external) resonance flows. All flows are doubly degenerate. Bessel function zeros are labelled by j_{p,q_i} , where $p \in \{m - 1, m, \dots\}$. Bound state flows occur between corresponding zeros of adjacent Bessel functions.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.12: Flow portraits in the kR [κR] plane for $m = 0$ in the upper [lower] panel. Labels q_i enumerate internal resonance flows. All flows are nondegenerate here. Bound state flows have been offset from the imaginary axis for clarity.

probability density functions appear for the various types of solution, *i.e.* resonances, bound states and quasi antibound states.

The bound state probability densities are typical in that the density is concentrated almost completely within the potential. The internal resonances show the expected leaky field patterns, and external resonances have their probability density mostly beyond the range of the potential. The quasi antibound states resemble bound states which exponentially diverge outside the well, as one would expect for an antibound state. The probability densities, as one would expect, are highly sensitive to both the strength of the potential and the modulus of the imaginary part of the wavenumber.

4.3 Summary

The solutions of the circular well exhibit rich dynamical behaviour. In the kR plane we see the emergence of attracting cycles and splitting flows that recombine to somehow encourage generation of new bound states from the origin. We need to consider multiple sheets of the Riemann surface of the resonance condition to see the full picture for the odd case. There is still some detail missing related to the mechanism behind creation of bound states from the origin. The κR plane has again demonstrated its utility by separating out the orbits of bound states and describing their infinite potential limit by means of attracting zeros of Bessel functions. The richness of the potentiodynamics of the states is a testament to the fact that simply moving from one dimension to two dimensions can introduce surprising depth to the problem.

Figure 4.13: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential well of depth $V_0 = 10$ [$V_0 = 80$] on the left [right] for the first (only) external ($q_e = 1$) resonance. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the well boundary.

Figure 4.14: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential well of depth $V_0 = 10$. The left [right] panel shows the first [second] internal ($q_i = 1$ [$q_i = 2$]) resonance. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the well boundary.

Figure 4.15: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential well of depth $V_0 = 80$. The left [right] panel shows the ground [first excited] bound state. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the well boundary.

Figure 4.16: Probability density plots for the case $m = 3$ for a potential well of depth $V_0 = 80$. The left [right] panel shows the first [second] quasi-antibound state. High (low) density shown as dark (light). The black dotted ring at $r = 1$ is the well boundary.

Chapter 5

Two Dimensional Elliptic Barriers

In this chapter, we reach the most complicated potential studied in this work. We examine the case of repulsive elliptic potentials (barriers) as a generalisation of the circular case, and check our results by reproducing the circular barrier results in the circular limit of eccentricity approaching 1. The analysis of such elliptic systems is markedly more complicated than the special case of a circle, due to the inevitable appearance of Mathieu functions of various kinds, which are notorious in mathematical physics for being difficult to work with computationally. Undeterred, a significant time investment of the project was focussed on understanding Mathieu functions, and preparing a library of them which was compatible with complex arguments in order to accommodate the complex wavenumbers we have been using to search for resonances, as no routines with this feature were readily available in any of the common special function libraries that we could find. The implementation of Mathieu functions of complex parameter was not without its issues, and as we will soon see, computational issues with branch cuts were a persistent hindrance, which is why the elliptic well was left untreated in this current work. Plans for future work will be discussed in Chapter 6.

Figure 5.1: Schematic of the elliptic barrier. The top figures show vertical cross sections along the x and y axes, and the bottom figure shows a top down view of the system. The barrier has height V_0 .

5.1 Elliptic potential

The potential barriers of interest are ellipses of semi-major axis a and semi-minor axis b , of height V_0 , centred at the origin. These are described in Cartesian coordinates by

$$V(x, y) = \begin{cases} V_0, & \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{b}\right)^2 < 1, \\ 0, & \left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{b}\right)^2 > 1. \end{cases} \quad (5.1)$$

A schematic of the barrier is shown in Fig. (5.1). As ever, we use Rydberg units, and seek complex eigenvalues of the time-independent Schrödinger equation

$$[-\nabla^2 + V(x, y)] \psi_n(x, y) = \mathcal{E}_n \psi_n(x, y), \quad (5.2)$$

Figure 5.2: Elliptic coordinate grid, *i.e.* lines of constant coordinates. Constant μ are confocal ellipses, and constant $|\nu|$ are confocal hyperbolae. The thick line shows a degenerate ellipse.

subject to continuity of the wavefunction and its derivative, or equivalently continuity of the logarithmic derivative, around the elliptic boundary, as well as the outgoing wave boundary condition at infinity. This ensures the solutions we seek are the resonances in the fourth quadrant of the complex k plane.

The usual reformulation of Eq. (5.2) is as a pair of Helmholtz equations

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\nabla^2 + k_n^2] \psi_n^{(1)}(x, y) &= 0, \\
 [\nabla^2 + \kappa_n^2] \psi_n^{(2)}(x, y) &= 0, \\
 \kappa &= \sqrt{k^2 - V_0}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5.3}$$

In Eq. (5.3), the indices (1) and (2) respectively denote solutions outside and inside the range of the potential barrier. The elliptic geometry of the barrier obliges the

application of elliptic coordinates (μ, ν) , where μ is the radial variable and takes values $0 \leq \mu < \infty$, and ν is the angular coordinate and takes values $0 \leq \nu < 2\pi$. The relationship between elliptic and Cartesian coordinates is given by

$$\begin{aligned}x &= l \cosh \mu \cos \nu, \\y &= l \sinh \mu \sin \nu.\end{aligned}\tag{5.4}$$

In Eq. (5.4), l is the focal length of the ellipse, which is related to its semi-axes by $l = \sqrt{a^2 - b^2}$. The coordinate lines correspond to confocal ellipses of constant μ , and confocal hyperbolae of constant $|\nu|$. An elliptic coordinate grid is shown in Fig. (5.2). Comparing these equations with the equation of the ellipse in standard position, we identify $a = l \cosh \mu$, and $b = l \sinh \mu$. It follows that the boundary of the ellipse at $\mu = U$ is given by

$$U = \tanh^{-1} \left(\frac{b}{a} \right).\tag{5.5}$$

Using the appropriate scale factors, the Laplacian in the elliptic coordinate system can be expressed as (Willatzen and Hoon, 2011)

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{l^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \cosh^2 \mu)} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \mu^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \nu^2} \right).\tag{5.6}$$

With this expression, Eq. (5.3) can be recast in elliptic coordinates as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \mu^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \nu^2} + l^2 k^2 (\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu) \psi(\mu, \nu) = 0.\tag{5.7}$$

Recalling the power reduction hyperbolic and trigonometric identities

$$\begin{aligned}\sinh^2 \mu &\equiv \frac{\cosh(2\mu) - 1}{2}, \\ \sin^2 \nu &\equiv \frac{1 - \cos(2\nu)}{2},\end{aligned}\tag{5.8}$$

Eq. (5.7) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \mu^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \nu^2} + \frac{l^2 k^2}{2} [\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \psi(\mu, \nu) = 0. \quad (5.9)$$

We perform a separation of variables, splitting ψ into radial and angular parts, *i.e.* we take take ansatz $\psi(\mu, \nu) = g(\nu)f(\mu)$. There is a serious caveat here: although the Helmholtz equation and relevant boundary conditions are separable in elliptic coordinates, the separation constants are region dependent, *i.e.* we need a different constant inside and outside the barrier. The boundary value problem on a one coordinate surface is formally not separable in this case. We nevertheless argue that because we are principally interested in the limiting cases of extremely high barriers and ellipses with very modest eccentricities, the results that follow from this assumption of separability are useful approximations to the true solutions, a fact we will demonstrate by recovering the circular barrier results in the limit of eccentricity going to zero. We proceed undeterred for now and make further comment later. Substituting into Eq. (5.9), we have

$$g(\nu) \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \mu^2} + f(\mu) \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \nu^2} + \frac{l^2 k^2}{2} [\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] f(\mu)g(\nu) = 0. \quad (5.10)$$

Equivalently, we have

$$\frac{1}{f(\mu)} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \mu^2} + \frac{1}{g(\nu)} \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \nu^2} + \frac{l^2 k^2}{2} [\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] = 0, \quad (5.11)$$

which, after isolating terms in μ and ν gives

$$\frac{1}{f(\mu)} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial \mu^2} + \frac{l^2 k^2}{2} \cosh(2\mu) = -\frac{1}{g(\nu)} \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial \nu^2} - \frac{l^2 k^2}{2} \cos(2\nu). \quad (5.12)$$

The only way for Eq. (5.12) to hold for all values of μ and ν is if both sides are equal to a constant, λ (in fact we will see that λ is not a constant at all, but a function of the wavenumber and ellipticity, which is reflected in the breakdown of the separability

of the problem). Then, after some minor adjustments, we obtain a pair of ordinary differential equations. The angular equation is

$$\frac{d^2g}{d\nu^2} + [\lambda - 2q \cos(2\nu)]g(\nu) = 0, \quad (5.13)$$

which is the Mathieu equation, and the radial equation is

$$\frac{d^2f}{d\mu^2} - [\lambda - 2q \cosh(2\mu)]f(\mu) = 0, \quad (5.14)$$

which is known as the modified Mathieu equation. In Eqs. (5.13) and (5.14)

$$q \equiv \frac{l^2 k^2}{4}, \quad l^2 = a^2 - b^2, \quad (5.15)$$

and λ is the separation constant. Due to the physical implications of these differential equations, Eq. (5.13) is sometimes referred to as the Angular Mathieu equation, and Eq. (5.14) as the Radial Mathieu equation. The solutions of the respective equations can then be referred to as Angular and Radial Mathieu functions.

Solutions of Eq. (5.13), the Angular Mathieu equation, are only physically significant here when they are periodic. Periodic solutions of this equation are manifest only for a special set of separation constant values $\{\lambda_m\}$, where m is a non-negative integer, which is how angular quantisation naturally arises in this system, as the quantum number m carries through into Eq. (5.14). To see why the range of m is constrained in this way, one needs to consider only the special case of a circle, where $a = b$, meaning l , and by extension q vanishes. Then the Angular Mathieu equation reduces to the trivial equation

$$\frac{d^2g}{d\nu^2} + \lambda g(\nu) = 0, \quad (5.16)$$

whose solutions are ordinary circular trigonometric functions, $\sin(\sqrt{\lambda}\nu)$ and $\cos(\sqrt{\lambda}\nu)$. In order that these solutions are 2π periodic, $\lambda = m^2$, where $m = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. The Angular Mathieu functions can be classified both by their parity, and by the parity of

the angular quantum number, m . The solutions are such that for m even, the solutions are π periodic, and they are 2π periodic for m odd. We denote these Angular Mathieu functions by

$$g(\nu) = \begin{cases} \text{ce}_m(\nu, q), \\ \text{se}_m(\nu, q), \end{cases} \quad (5.17)$$

which are respectively named the elliptic cosine and elliptic sine. These are elliptic analogues of standard circular trigonometric functions, and reduce to their namesakes in the circular limit, *i.e.* $\text{ce}_m(\nu, q) \rightarrow \cos(m\nu)$ and $\text{se}_m(\nu, q) \rightarrow \sin(m\nu)$ as $b \rightarrow a$.

On the other hand, the Radial Mathieu functions, which are the solutions of the Radial Mathieu Equation, Eq. (5.14), we denote

$$f(\mu) = \begin{cases} \text{MC}_m^{(j)}(\mu, q), \\ \text{MS}_m^{(j)}(\mu, q), \end{cases} \quad (5.18)$$

which are even and odd respectively. The superscript j determines which kind of Radial Mathieu function is meant, with $j = 1$ corresponding to the elliptic analogue of a Bessel function (of the first kind), J_m , and $j = 3$ referring to the elliptic analogue of an (outgoing) Hankel function, $H_m^{(1)}$. These analogies with the more familiar cylinder functions will be helpful later when we discuss the results, and in particular when we compare the elliptic results with the special case of a circle. Computational details of the Mathieu functions are postponed until the next section. To find the resonance condition, we impose as usual the continuity of the logarithmic derivative of the coordinate wavefunction, this time around the elliptic boundary $\mu = U$. This gives

$$\left. \frac{\partial \ln \psi_m^{(1)}(\mu, \nu)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} = \left. \frac{\partial \ln \psi_m^{(2)}(\mu, \nu)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U}, \quad (5.19)$$

where (1) and (2) refer to wavefunctions in the internal and external region respectively.

Assuming our separation of variables to be valid therefore leads to the even wavefunction

$$\psi_m(\mu, \nu) = \begin{cases} N_m \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(\mu, Q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, Q), & \mu \leq U, \\ N_m \text{MC}_m^{(3)}(\mu, q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, q), & \mu > U, \end{cases} \quad (5.20)$$

and an analogous result for the odd wavefunction, where N_m is a normalisation constant. In fact, this cannot be the true wavefunction since requiring continuity at the boundary leads to a condition that cannot be satisfied for arbitrary ν ! In fact, even though this is not the correct wavefunction, it furnishes us with a suitable basis in which to expand the true solution (Willatzen and Hoon, 2011). The appropriate (even) wavefunction is then

$$\Psi(\mu, \nu) = \begin{cases} \sum_m a_m \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(\mu, Q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, Q), & \mu \leq U, \\ \sum_m b_m \text{MC}_m^{(3)}(\mu, q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, q), & \mu > U, \end{cases}. \quad (5.21)$$

The actual (even) boundary conditions would then be given by

$$\sum_m a_m \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(U, Q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, Q) = \sum_m b_m \text{MC}_m^{(3)}(U, q) \text{ce}_m(\nu, q), \quad (5.22)$$

and

$$\sum_m a_m \left. \frac{\partial \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(\mu, Q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} \text{ce}_m(\nu, Q) = \sum_m b_m \left. \frac{\partial \text{MC}_m^{(3)}(\mu, q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} \text{ce}_m(\nu, q). \quad (5.23)$$

This pair of equations is extremely non-trivial to solve numerically with reasonable speed, even with Julia and the procedures of Chapter 1. This is the principal reason why we constrain our attention to the case where we incorrectly push the separability and treat only modest eccentricities for approximate results that can be built on in future work.

Our approximate (artificially separated) forms for the even and odd resonance con-

dition are given by

$$\text{MC}_m^{(3)}(U, q) \left. \frac{\partial \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(\mu, Q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} - \text{MC}_m^{(1)}(U, Q) \left. \frac{\partial \text{MC}_m^{(3)}(\mu, q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} = 0, \quad (5.24)$$

and

$$\text{MS}_m^{(3)}(U, q) \left. \frac{\partial \text{MS}_m^{(1)}(\mu, Q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} - \text{MS}_m^{(1)}(U, Q) \left. \frac{\partial \text{MS}_m^{(3)}(\mu, q)}{\partial \mu} \right|_{\mu=U} = 0, \quad (5.25)$$

where

$$Q \equiv \frac{l^2 \kappa^2}{4}, \quad l^2 = a^2 - b^2. \quad (5.26)$$

Only the solutions in the fourth quadrant of the k plane will be of interest here, since this potential will not support bound states, meaning that there will be no resonances lost as the parameters are varied.

5.2 Mathieu functions

In order to work with the Mathieu functions of complex argument computationally, we need to understand how to construct useful representations of them (Hamid et al., 2002). For the Angular Mathieu functions, we already argued that periodic solutions are necessary. Hence, we can search for a Fourier Series representation

$$g(\nu) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{A_n \cos(n\nu) + B_n \sin(n\nu)\}, \quad (5.27)$$

which, after differentiating gives

$$\frac{dg}{d\nu} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{nB_n \cos(n\nu) - nA_n \sin(n\nu)\}, \quad (5.28)$$

and

$$\frac{d^2g}{d\nu^2} = - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{n^2 A_n \cos(n\nu) + n^2 B_n \sin(n\nu)\}. \quad (5.29)$$

We substitute into Eq. (5.13) to yield

$$\begin{aligned} & - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{n^2 A_n \cos(n\nu) + n^2 B_n \sin(n\nu)\} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{\lambda A_n \cos(n\nu) + \lambda B_n \sin(n\nu)\} \\ & - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{2q A_n \cos(2\nu) \cos(n\nu) + 2q B_n \cos(2\nu) \sin(n\nu)\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.30)$$

Employing product-to-sum trigonometric identities

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta) &= \frac{1}{2} [\cos(\alpha + \beta) + \cos(\alpha - \beta)], \\ \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) &= \frac{1}{2} [\sin(\alpha + \beta) + \sin(\alpha - \beta)], \end{aligned} \quad (5.31)$$

we can collect terms in Eq. (5.30) as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{(\lambda - n^2) A_n \cos(2\nu) - q[A_n \cos((n+2)\nu) + A_n \cos((n-2)\nu)]\} \\ & + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{(\lambda - n^2) B_n \sin(n\nu) - q[B_n \sin((n+2)\nu) + B_n \sin((n-2)\nu)]\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.32)$$

Shifting the summation indices to gather terms in $\cos(n\nu)$ and $\sin(n\nu)$, with the stipulation that A_{-n} and B_{-n} are identically zero for $n > 0$ and $B_0 = 0$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=-2}^{\infty} \{(\lambda - n^2) A_n - q[A_{n-2} + A_{n+2}]\} \cos(n\nu) \\ & + \sum_{n=-1}^{\infty} \{(\lambda - n^2) B_n - q[B_{n-2} + B_{n+2}]\} \sin(n\nu) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.33)$$

Equating coefficients for $\cos n\nu$ and $\sin n\nu$ results in 4 sets of recurrence relations, relating the sets of coefficients $\{A_n\}$ and $\{B_n\}$, with even and odd values of the index, n .

The even function coefficients of even order, A_{2s} , can be determined from arbitrary A_0 by

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda A_0 - qA_2 &= 0, \\ (\lambda - 4)A_2 - q(2A_0 + A_4) &= 0, \\ (\lambda - (2s)^2)A_{2s} - q(A_{2s-2} + A_{2s+2}) &= 0, \quad (s \geq 2),\end{aligned}\tag{5.34}$$

and then normalised according to the relationship

$$2|A_0|^2 + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} |A_{2s}|^2 = 1.\tag{5.35}$$

Then the even Angular Mathieu function of even order can be written as

$$ce_{2s}(\nu, q) = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} A_{2s}(q) \cos(2s\nu),\tag{5.36}$$

noticing that the Fourier coefficients depend in general on q .

Similarly, the coefficients A_{2s+1} are determined from a value of A_1 , along with the recurrence relationship

$$\begin{aligned}(\lambda - 1 - q)A_1 - qA_3 &= 0, \\ (\lambda - (2s + 1)^2)A_{2s+1} - q(A_{2s+3} + A_{2s-1}) &= 0, \quad (s \geq 1),\end{aligned}\tag{5.37}$$

and normalised according to

$$\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} |A_{2s+1}|^2 = 1.\tag{5.38}$$

The even Angular Mathieu function of odd order is then

$$ce_{2s+1}(\nu, q) = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} A_{2s+1}(q) \cos((2s + 1)\nu).\tag{5.39}$$

The coefficients B_{2s+1} are found from B_1 and

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda - 1 + q)B_1 - qB_3 &= 0, \\ (\lambda - (2s + 1)^2)B_{2s+1} - q(B_{2s+3} + B_{2s-1}) &= 0, \quad (s \geq 1), \end{aligned} \quad (5.40)$$

obeying

$$\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} |B_{2s+1}|^2 = 1, \quad (5.41)$$

and the odd-odd Angular Mathieu function is

$$\text{se}_{2s+1}(\nu, q) = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} B_{2s+1}(q) \sin((2s + 1)\nu). \quad (5.42)$$

Finally, the odd-even function has coefficients governed by

$$\begin{aligned} (\lambda - 4)B_2 - qB_4 &= 0, \\ (\lambda - (2s + 2)^2)B_{2s+2} - q(B_{2s} + B_{2s+4}) &= 0, \quad (s \geq 1), \end{aligned} \quad (5.43)$$

with

$$\sum_{s=0}^{\infty} |B_{2s+2}|^2 = 1, \quad (5.44)$$

and the odd-even Angular Mathieu function is

$$\text{se}_{2s+2} = \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} B_{2s+2}(q) \sin((2s + 2)\nu). \quad (5.45)$$

The functions of even order have period π , and those with odd order have period 2π .

The function $\text{se}_0 = 0$.

In order to determine the characteristic values $\lambda(q)$ (which clearly depend on q , as mentioned earlier), and the appropriate set of Fourier coefficients in an efficient way, one can recast the recurrence relations in the Eqs. (5.34), (5.37), (5.40) and (5.43), and compute both simultaneously using the efficient routines for finding eigenvalues

and eigenvectors. These matrices are rather nice in that they are banded, symmetric, tridiagonal matrices, and optimised routines for computing the eigenstructure of these matrices are in common use. The eigenvalue equations are

a) even-even, period π

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\lambda_{2s} & \sqrt{2}q & 0 & & & \\ \sqrt{2}q & 4 - \lambda_{2s} & q & & & \\ 0 & q & 4^2 - \lambda_{2s} & q & & \\ & & & \ddots & & \\ & & & & q & \\ q & & & & & (2N)^2 - \lambda_{2s} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2}A_0^{2s} \\ A_2^{2s} \\ A_4^{2s} \\ \vdots \\ A_{2N}^{2s} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (5.46)$$

b) even-odd, period 2π

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 + q - \lambda_{2s+1} & q & 0 & & & \\ q & 3^2 - \lambda_{2s+1} & q & & & \\ 0 & & & \ddots & & \\ & & & & q & \\ q & & & & & (2N + 1)^2 - \lambda_{2s+1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_1^{2s+1} \\ A_3^{2s+1} \\ \vdots \\ A_{2N+1}^{2s+1} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (5.47)$$

c) odd-odd, period 2π

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - q - \lambda_{2s+1} & q & 0 & & & \\ q & 3^2 - \lambda_{2s+1} & q & & & \\ 0 & & & \ddots & & \\ & & & & q & \\ q & & & & & (2N + 1)^2 - \lambda_{2s+1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_1^{2s+1} \\ B_3^{2s+1} \\ \vdots \\ B_{2N+1}^{2s+1} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (5.48)$$

d) odd-even, period π

$$\begin{pmatrix} 4 - \lambda_{2s+2} & q & 0 & & & \\ q & 16 - \lambda_{2s+2} & q & & & \\ 0 & & & \ddots & & \\ & & & & q & \\ q & & & & & (2N+2)^2 - \lambda_{2s+2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_2^{2s+2} \\ B_4^{2s+2} \\ \vdots \\ B_{2N+2}^{2s+2} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (5.49)$$

The Angular Mathieu equation, Eq. (5.13) becomes the Radial Mathieu equation, Eq. (5.14) under the change of variables $\nu \rightarrow i\mu$. Thus, this transformation converts the Fourier series representations of the Angular functions to Radial functions expressed as hyperbolic series, which are not acceptable for numerical computation as they have unfavourable convergence properties. In fact, it is common practice to re-express these hyperbolic expansions as series involving products of cylinder functions which feature the same expansion coefficients as the Angular functions.

One way to express these so-called Bessel product series follows, where $Z_n^{(j)}$ means J_n when $j = 1$ and $H_n^{(1)}$ when $j = 3$, and $u_1 = \sqrt{q}e^{-\mu}$ and $u_2 = \sqrt{q}e^{\mu}$, and we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MC}_{2s}^{(j)}(\mu, q) &= \frac{1}{A_0^{2s}(q)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+s} A_{2n}^{2s}(q) J_n(u_1) Z_n^{(j)}(u_2), \\ \text{MC}_{2s+1}^{(j)}(\mu, q) &= \frac{1}{A_1^{2s+1}(q)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+s} A_{2n+1}^{2s+1}(q) \left[J_n(u_1) Z_{n+1}^{(j)}(u_2) + J_{n+1}(u_1) Z_n^{(j)}(u_2) \right], \\ \text{MS}_{2s+1}^{(j)}(\mu, q) &= \frac{1}{B_1^{2s+1}(q)} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+s} B_{2n+1}^{2s+1}(q) \left[J_n(u_1) Z_{n+1}^{(j)}(u_2) - J_{n+1}(u_1) Z_n^{(j)}(u_2) \right], \\ \text{MS}_{2s+2}^{(j)}(\mu, q) &= \frac{1}{B_2^{2s+2}(q)} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+s} B_{2n}^{2s+2}(q) \left[J_{n-1}(u_1) Z_{n+1}^{(j)}(u_2) - J_{n+1}(u_1) Z_{n-1}^{(j)}(u_2) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.50)$$

There also exist several integral representations, both as integrals over finite domains and as improper integrals for these Radial functions, as well as alternative summation representations.

One simply needs to differentiate the series representations in Eqs. (5.50) to produce the other functions used in the analysis. Further details about computation of these functions can be found in (Bibby and Peterson, 2014; Gutiérrez-Vega et al., 2003; Abramowitz and Stegun, 1972; McLachlan, 1947; Schneider and Marquardt, 1999), including alternative representations.

5.3 Flows for the elliptic barrier

One can now vary the barrier's height V_0 and eccentricity $e = \sqrt{1 - b^2/a^2}$ to trace the evolution of the resonances in the complex ka plane in response to these variations. The same data viewed in the alternative *potentiodynamic* κa plane will reveal more features of these resonances. We initially illustrate typical dynamics of the resonances using the angular quantum numbers $m = 2$ and $m = 3$, see Figs. (5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6), as representative examples. Then, we will examine the somewhat special cases of $m = 1$ and $m = 0$, see Figs. (5.7, 5.8).

Beginning with a barrier of effectively zero height, the flows traced out by the resonances as the barrier height is increased are plotted in the complex ka and κa planes for the limiting case of a circular barrier, $e = 0$ ($b = a$), and for elliptic barriers of eccentricities $e = 0.8$ ($b = 0.6a$) for $m = 2, 3$, and $e \cong 0.714$ ($b = 0.7a$) for $m = 1, 0$. For each barrier with eccentricity $e \neq 0$ there are two resonance flows unless $m = 0$. One flow is defined by the even resonance condition given by Eq. (5.24), while the other is defined by the odd resonance condition, Eq. (5.25). The special case $m = 0$ is different because there is just a single resonance flow for any given value of eccentricity, which is borne out mathematically by the fact that only the even resonance condition exists for this case.

The trajectories, referred to as *eccentricipaths*, traced out by the resonances as the eccentricity of the barrier is increased, so that the flow of the circular barrier resonances

meets the corresponding flows of the elliptic barrier, are plotted in the complex ka and κa planes for the fixed values of barrier height, $V_0 = 5$ and $V_0 = 50$.

The resonances of a circular barrier with $m > 0$ are doubly degenerate. If one perturbs the rotational symmetry by vertically squashing the circle into an ellipse, the degeneracy is lifted and therefore each *eccentripath* splits into two, with the exception of $m = 0$, see Fig. (5.8).

There are two different categories of resonances, classified by their limiting flow behaviours, as well as by the appearance of their probability densities.

The first type are known as external resonances, and these manifest only for $m \geq 2$. There are only finitely many of these, with the quantity given by the integer part of $m/2$, *i.e.* there are 0 for $m = 0$ or $m = 1$, 1 for $m = 2$ or $m = 3$, 2 for $m = 4$ or $m = 5$, *etc.* The probability densities for external resonances lie essentially fully beyond the range of the potential, which accounts for their name. As $V_0 \rightarrow \infty$, the ρ_e -th external resonance of a circular barrier approaches the ρ_e -th zero of the Hankel function $H_m^{(1)}(ka)$ in the k plane, labelled as $h_{m,\rho_e}^{(1)}$. The even {odd} external resonances of an elliptic barrier approach the elliptical analogues of Hankel function zeros, which turn out to be zeros of even {odd} Mathieu-Hankel functions, $MC_m^{(3)}(U, q)$ and $MS_m^{(3)}(U, q)$, for the particular ellipse, denoted by $mc_{m,\rho_e}^{(3)}$ and $ms_{m,\rho_e}^{(3)}$. The pair of subscripts in the above zeros respectively indicate the value of m and the numbering ρ_e of the external resonance. The attractor effect of these zeros for external resonance flows is shown in the top panels of Figs. (5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6).

Internal resonances by contrast are characterised by their probability densities having an evanescent presence within the range of the potential. They are infinite in number regardless of m and their flows approach real infinity asymptotically in the complex k plane when $V_0 \rightarrow \infty$, see the upper panels in Figs. (5.3, 5.5, 5.7, 5.8).

When examined in the complex κa plane, a markedly different picture emerges for

internal resonances, which is very elegant in the sense that it is dual to the behaviour of external resonances in the ka plane. In this potentiodynamic coordinate system, the flows of internal resonances asymptotically approach real-valued zeros j_{m,ρ_i} of Bessel functions $J_m(\kappa a)$ for a circular barrier ($b = a$) and real-valued zeros $mc_{m,\rho_i}^{(1)}$, $ms_{m,\rho_i}^{(1)}$ of Mathieu-Bessel functions $MC_m^{(1)}(U, Q)$, $MS_m^{(1)}(U, Q)$ for elliptic barriers, see the lower panels in Figs. (5.3, 5.5, 5.7, 5.8).

It is illuminating to note the probability densities, and particularly how they change as the circular potential deforms into an ellipse. A Cartesian grid was mapped onto elliptic coordinates using a novel transformation technique (Sun, 2017) and used to compute probability density plots shown in Figs. (5.9, 5.10). The probability densities are shown for a barrier of height $V_0 = 50$, for the circular case, $b = a$ ($e = 0$), a slightly deformed case, $b = 0.95a$ ($e \approx 0.31$), and a case with a larger deformation, $b = 0.7a$ ($e \approx 0.71$), all with $m = 2$ as a representative example, for the first {second} internal resonances. These eccentricity values were chosen to best reveal the salient features along the $V_0 = 50$ eccentricity paths. The eccentricity increases in Figs. (5.9, 5.10) from (a) to (c) to (e) along the even resonance eccentricity path, and from (b) to (d) to (f) along the odd eccentricity path; see the eccentricity paths for $V_0 = 50$ in the upper panel of Fig. (5.3). To capture the effect of eccentricity on the probability densities, it was necessary to choose the angular eigenfunctions of the circular case to be $\cos m\nu$ and $\sin m\nu$ in order to bring these into direct correspondence with the elliptic case.

Figs. (5.9, 5.10) show that the resonant wavefunctions become progressively more anisotropic as the eccentricity increases. The even parity probability densities are more sensitive to the elliptic perturbation than the odd ones. As the elliptic potential under consideration is a repulsive type (barrier), the system cannot support bound states. It should be again emphasised that any probability density lying inside the barrier is much smaller than the density lying away from the barrier. The densities grow rapidly with distance from the barrier, indicative of resonances, and in contrast to bound states. In plotting these probability densities, we had to re-normalize the contributions that exist

inside the barrier in order to make them visible at all.

5.4 Summary

The generalisation of the circular barrier results outlined from Chapter 3 to the elliptic case presented herein forms a rather elegant picture, which reveals once more a duality in the behaviour of both types of resonances in the ka and κa planes. The κa plane is the quantum mechanical analogue of the kn coordinates one can use in optical problems, where n is the refractive index of an optical resonator (Dettmann et al., 2009a,b). The deformation of the geometry from circular to elliptic lifts degeneracy for all $m > 0$, and produces highly anisotropic probability densities. The use of performant programming routines has optimised numerical computation to such a level that one need not avoid using the various Mathieu functions. In future work we hope to look at the resonance dynamics of potentials with more intricate geometries, whose equations for resonance involve even more exotic special functions than Mathieu functions. A study of elliptic potentials involving point scatterers would also likely be a fruitful study. Relevant resources for further quantum mechanical problems with elliptic geometry are (Grbić, 2019; van den Broek and Peeters, 2001; Waalkens et al., 1997).

We stress again that the results presented herein are approximations that can be expected to be useful only for small perturbations from circular geometry. In fact, the true solutions invoke infinite superpositions of Mathieu functions, which become extremely difficult to work with numerically. At the level of detail involved in this work it became all but impossible to use Maple or Mathematica to undertake the numerical computation with Mathieu functions, and we were only able to complete calculations in a reasonable amount of time owing to the floating point operation performance of Julia. To investigate superpositions of Mathieu functions required to solve the ‘real’ resonance conditions, even the efficient procedures detailed in Chapter 1 in Julia become too slow

to be acceptable. Our glimmer of hope for making progress here is to fully implement Kowalczyk's procedure (Kowalczyk, 2015), using a self adaptive mesh generated from Delaunay triangulation rather than a naive rectangulation of the plane. See Chapter 6 for some further details.

Figure 5.3: Flows of the external, $\rho_e = 1$, and the first {second} internal, $\rho_i = 1\{2\}$, resonances for $m = 2$, with arrows showing the direction of increasing potential from $V_0 \cong 0$ to effectively infinite V_0 , where the external flows reach their limit points $h_{2,1}^{(1)}$, $mc_{2,1}^{(3)}$, $ms_{2,1}^{(3)}$ in the k plane, and the internal flows reach their limit points $j_{2,1\{2\}}$, $mc_{2,1\{2\}}^{(1)}$, $ms_{2,1\{2\}}^{(1)}$ in the κ plane; thin grey curve - resonances of a circular barrier ($b = a$); thick grey {black} curve - even {odd} resonances of an elliptic barrier ($b = 0.6a$). The eccentricpaths for $V_0 = 5, 50$ are shown by thick grey {black} curves without arrows.

Figure 5.4: A closer look at the flows of the external resonances, shown in Fig. (5.3).

Figure 5.5: Same as Fig. (5.3), but with $m = 3$.

Figure 5.6: A closer look at the flows of the external resonances, shown in Fig. (5.5).

Figure 5.7: Same as Fig. (5.3), but with $m = 1$ and $b = 0.7a$. Note that there are no external resonances.

Figure 5.8: Same as Fig. (5.3), but with $m = 0$ and $b = 0.7a$. Note that there are no external resonances and only even internal resonances exist for this non-degenerate case.

Figure 5.9: Probability density plots of the first internal resonance ($\rho_i = 1$) for $m = 2$, for a barrier of height $V_0 = 50$. The semi-major axis of the ellipse is fixed at $a = 1$, while the semi-minor axis b of the ellipse is varied. The angular contributions to the probability density are listed below, along with the values of b . Note that $\tilde{q} = Q \{ \tilde{q} = q \}$ for $\mu \leq U$ $\{ \mu > U \}$.

- (a) $b = a$ (circular barrier), $|\cos(2\nu)|^2$;
 - (b) $b = a$ (circular barrier), $|\sin(2\nu)|^2$;
 - (c) $b = 0.95a$ (slightly perturbed elliptic barrier), $|\text{ce}_2(\nu, \tilde{q})|^2$;
 - (d) $b = 0.95a$ (slightly perturbed elliptic barrier), $|\text{se}_2(\nu, \tilde{q})|^2$;
 - (e) $b = 0.7a$ (strongly perturbed elliptic barrier), $|\text{ce}_2(\nu, \tilde{q})|^2$;
 - (f) $b = 0.7a$ (strongly perturbed elliptic barrier), $|\text{se}_2(\nu, \tilde{q})|^2$.
- Dark colour indicates higher probability density.

Figure 5.10: Same as Figure 5.9, but for the second internal resonance ($\rho_i = 2$).

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Work

The orbits of states in the k and κ planes exhibit rich dynamical behaviour, replete with attracting and repelling points which promise insights into why flow trajectories appear as they do. The κ plane is a useful new tool for numerically probing the limiting behaviour of states for potentials of infinite strength.

There is great scope for future work in related areas. A highly promising class of two-dimensional potentials are the so-called super-ellipses, which are shapes satisfying

$$\left|\frac{x}{a}\right|^n + \left|\frac{y}{b}\right|^n = 1, \quad (6.1)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ and $a, b > 0$. A possible strategy could be some kind of perturbative scheme, where we consider

$$\left|\frac{x}{a}\right|^{(2+\varepsilon)} + \left|\frac{y}{b}\right|^{(2+\varepsilon)} = 1, \quad (6.2)$$

and begin the analysis with solutions of the elliptic potential as the unperturbed solutions in a similar fashion to (Antikainen et al., 2017).

A related structure is the ‘Fernández-Guasti Squirle’, which is a plane geometric

figure satisfying

$$x^2 + y^2 - \frac{s^2}{r^2} x^2 y^2 = r^2. \quad (6.3)$$

An analysis of the resonances of potentials with these geometries would be incredibly interesting, and would be a large step towards some general understanding of bounded two-dimensional potentials.

As mentioned in Chapter 5, the issues with computation of zeros of the determinants involving superpositions of Mathieu functions and their derivatives may be ameliorated by recourse to a more efficient root finding procedure. Instead of generating points on a naive rectangular mesh, it will likely be worth spending extra time computationally seeking an optimal mesh geometry to reduce the number of expensive function calls needed. The idea of the self-adaptive mesh produced by Delaunay triangulation due to Kowalczyk (Kowalczyk, 2015) is demonstrated for the example function of Chapter 1 in Fig. (6.1). This shows that the zero levels of the real and imaginary parts of the function produced by Wagon’s method using a rectangular mesh have been approximately found *in situ* using Kowalczyk’s algorithm for seeking a sparse self-adaptive mesh, rather than as a separate computation performed after evaluating the function of interest over a dense mesh. Although this procedure involves significant overhead to find such an optimal mesh, it is worth the extra time taken when each function call is as expensive as the Mathieu series. The mesh produced can be interpolated at low computational cost to produce the same contour lines, and then the crossing points of the contours can be found in much the same way as in Wagon’s method. Improving on the efficiency of this procedure should allow us to solve the true resonance condition to higher order than in Chapter 5. Kowalczyk also augmented his algorithm to facilitate root finding on functions with branch cuts, by creating a single-valued function composed of pointwise products over all Riemann sheets (Kowalczyk, 2017). The ability to remove the effect of branch cuts from the elliptic resonance condition would greatly reduce the complications we faced in the numerical work.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6.1: The lower panel is an illustration of the self-adaptive mesh produced by Kowalczyk's procedure. The black lines show a mesh produced by an adaptive Delaunay triangulation that is tailored to the function being analysed. This mesh has already identified the approximate locations of zero levels of the function's real and imaginary parts, which are shown in the top panel for the example function from Chapter 1.

In the future, the work could be extended by placing point scatterers into the 2D potentials, and deducing the effect of the scatterer's properties on the states.

Interesting three-dimensional structures are also something that could be looked at, particularly toroidal and ellipsoidal potentials.

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